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Dimensionality Reduction in Machine Learning: A Kernel-based Learning View on the Diffusion Maps Algorithm from Manifold Learning

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1. Introduction

In recent years, machine learning has made impressive progress due to the abundant availability of data and increased computational power. With the growing complexity and high-dimensionality of datasets, a crucial challenge arises: how can we effectively extract meaningful information from such vast amounts of data? Dimensionality reduction techniques play a key role in addressing this challenge by providing methods to transform high-dimensional data into a lower-dimensional representation while preserving or even enhancing its essential structure.

The significance of dimensionality reduction in machine learning cannot be overstated. These techniques offer several notable advantages by reducing the number of variables or features. Firstly, dimensionality reduction allows for visualization, which helps us gain insights into the underlying structure of the data. By projecting the data onto a lower-dimensional space, we can uncover patterns and relationships that would otherwise remain hidden in the original high-dimensional space. Visualizations aid in better understanding and interpretation of the data, supporting decision-making processes in various domains.

Secondly, dimensionality reduction techniques are crucial for enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of machine learning algorithms. The curse of dimensionality, a well-known phenomenon in high-dimensional spaces, presents substantial challenges. As the number of features increases, the density of data points becomes sparse, resulting in computational inefficiency and decreased algorithm performance. Dimensionality reduction can mitigate this issue by compressing the data into a lower-dimensional space, thereby reducing computational complexity and improving the scalability of machine learning algorithms.

In this thesis, we delve into the realm of dimensionality reduction in machine learning, with a particular focus on three prominent techniques: Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Kernel PCA, and the Diffusion Maps algorithm from Manifold Learning. These techniques have proven to be powerful tools for extracting relevant information and reducing the dimensionality of data.

PCA, a linear dimensionality reduction method, seeks to capture the most significant sources of variation in the data by finding a set of orthogonal axes, known as principal components. These components correspond to directions of maximum variance, enabling us to summarize the data's structure using fewer variables. PCA has found broad applicability across numerous domains and serves as a fundamental baseline technique for dimensionality reduction.

Building upon PCA, Kernel PCA incorporates the concept of kernel functions to capture nonlinear relationships and complex structures in the data. By mapping the data into a high-dimensional feature space, Kernel PCA can uncover intricate patterns that may not be apparent in the original space. The use of kernel functions introduces flexibility and

enables the discovery of nonlinear dependencies, making Kernel PCA a valuable tool for capturing the underlying structure of diverse datasets.

The Diffusion Maps algorithm from Manifold learning is another powerful technique for dimensionality reduction. It focuses on uncovering the intrinsic geometric structure and local relationships within complex datasets. By measuring the similarity between data points based on diffusion probabilities, Diffusion Maps construct a lower-dimensional representation that retains essential information about the data's underlying manifold, making it effective for handling nonlinear datasets and revealing hidden patterns.

In this thesis, we contribute to the field of dimensionality reduction by strengthening the theoretical foundations of these algorithms. We start by considering the case where we have perfect knowledge about the underlying data distribution and then extend our analysis to the sample case, where our knowledge is incomplete or limited. For Kernel PCA, we establish a rigorous functional analytic framework that establishes a strong connection with the associated kernel integral operator. In the case of the Diffusion Maps algorithm, we explore the intrinsic heat kernel of the manifold, which reveals a close connection to Brownian motion on the manifold and provides a better rationale for the construction of the Diffusion Maps algorithm. Additionally, we establish a novel and tight connection between Kernel PCA and the population case of the Diffusion Maps algorithm.

2. Principal Component Analysis in Hilbert Spaces

Principal component analysis (PCA) is a well-established linear dimensionality reduction method that has been widely used in various fields. It was first introduced by Karl Pearson in 1901 in his paper titled “*On Lines and Planes of Closest Fit to Systems of Points in Space*” [Pea01] and has since become one of the most popular techniques for dimensionality reduction.

In the classical setting, we have n data points X_1, \dots, X_n in \mathbb{R}^p , assumed to be sampled independent and identically from a probability distribution on \mathbb{R}^p , known as the population distribution. The goal of PCA is to project the data points onto d directions that capture the most variance in the data. To achieve this, we first estimate the empirical covariance matrix $\hat{\Sigma}_n$ using the data, defined as

$$\hat{\Sigma}_n := \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n (X_k - \bar{X}_n)(X_k - \bar{X}_n)^T,$$

where \bar{X}_n is the sample mean.

We then decompose $\hat{\Sigma}_n$ into its spectral decomposition

$$\hat{\Sigma}_n = \sum_{k=1}^p \hat{\sigma}_k^2 \hat{u}_k \hat{u}_k^T,$$

where the eigenvalues $(\hat{\sigma}_k^2)_{k=1}^p$ are ordered non-increasingly and the eigenvectors $(\hat{u}_k)_{k=1}^p$ are the empirical principal components.

In this section, we present a detailed explanation of PCA and its extension to a Hilbert space setting.

The Hilbert space generalization allows us to apply the theory of reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces (RKHS) from kernel-based learning to the PCA algorithm. As the latter just depends on the scalar product in a Hilbert space, the kernel trick can then be used. We will discuss kernel-based learning and kernel-PCA in the next section.

2.1. The Population Picture

In this section we will assume that we have exact knowledge of the distribution of the data vector X , which takes values in a separable Hilbert space \mathcal{H} . Specifically, X is a random variable that is measurable with respect to the Borel sigma algebra of \mathcal{H} , denoted as $B(\mathcal{H})$.

In the following discussion, we presume a prior understanding of Bochner integration theory applied to Banach space-valued functions, as exemplified in [AE09, Chapter 10].

Remark 2.1. It is noteworthy that we can assume the separability of \mathcal{H} without sacrificing generality. A Bochner-integrable function inherently takes on values in a separable subspace, allowing us to confine our focus to separable Hilbert spaces without loss of

generality.

Our first lemma addresses the conditions for the existence of the covariance operator and outlines its fundamental properties. Prior to that, we briefly introduce some notation that we will use throughout these thesis.

Consider $u, v \in \mathcal{H}$. When we write $|v\rangle\langle u|$, we are referring to a bounded linear operator defined as follows:

$$|v\rangle\langle u| : \begin{cases} \mathcal{H} & \rightarrow & \mathcal{H} \\ x & \mapsto & \langle u|x\rangle_{\mathcal{H}} v. \end{cases}$$

Here, $\langle u|x\rangle_{\mathcal{H}}$ denotes the standard inner product within the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} . This notation is borrowed from the 'Bra-Ket' notation, as introduced by physicist PAUL DIRAC in quantum mechanics.

Furthermore, we define the expectation value of a Banach space valued random variable X as $E(X) := \int_{\Omega} X(\omega)P(d\omega)$, where (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) denotes the underlying probability space on which X is defined.

Lemma 2.2 (Existence and properties of the covariance operator):

Let $X \in L^2(P; \mathcal{H})$. Then the covariance operator

$$\Sigma := E(|X - E(X)\rangle\langle X - E(X)|),$$

is well-defined. Furthermore, it is a self-adjoint, positive semidefinite trace class operator.

Proof. To prove this, we consider the random operator $S_X := |X - E(X)\rangle\langle X - E(X)|$, which is a self-adjoint, positive semidefinite operator of rank 1. Since it has finite rank, it is also a trace-class operator, and its trace-norm is given by

$$\|S_X\|_{\mathcal{N}(\mathcal{H})} = \text{tr}(|S_X|) = \text{tr}(S_X) = \|X - E(X)\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2.$$

That way, we see that the random operator S_X , which takes values in the Banach space of trace class operators $\mathcal{N}(\mathcal{H})$ (see [Wer18, p. 311, Satz VI.5.3 (c)]), is integrable, i.e. $S_X \in L^1(P; \mathcal{N}(\mathcal{H}))$.

Consequently, the Bochner-Lebesgue integral over S_X exists, yielding the covariance operator $\Sigma = E(S_X)$. This also shows, that Σ is, as an integral of trace class operators, itself a trace class operator. It is further clear, that Σ inherits its self-adjointness and positive semidefiniteness directly from the random operator S_X . \square

After clarifying the conditions under which Σ exists, we will from now on assume always without further notice $X \in L^2(P; \mathcal{H})$.

2.1.1. Variance-based Interpretation of PCA

This section introduces the variance-based interpretation of PCA, which involves identifying the directions of maximal variance in high-dimensional data.

The covariance operator is as a trace class operator especially compact. That means we can use the Spectral Theorem for self-adjoint compact operators A.1 and decompose:

$$\Sigma = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sigma_k^2 |u_k\rangle \langle u_k|, \quad (1)$$

whereby the eigenvalues are ordered descendingly $\sigma_1^2 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_k^2 \geq \dots \geq 0$. We assume that the orthonormal system $(u_k)_{k=1}^{\infty}$ is an orthonormal basis since we could complete it to one by adding an orthonormal basis of $\ker(\Sigma)$ and set the corresponding eigenvalues to 0. We call u_k the k -th principal component.

The eigenvalues are written in this suggestive form since they are exactly the variances of X along the principal components:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Var}(\langle u_k, X \rangle) &= E\left(|\langle u_k, X - E(X) \rangle|^2\right) \\ &= \langle u_k | E(|X - E(X)\rangle \langle X - E(X)|) |u_k\rangle \\ &= \langle u_k, \Sigma u_k \rangle = \sigma_k^2. \end{aligned}$$

This above spectral decomposition of the covariance operator Σ gives rise to a new coordinate system centered at $E(X)$ with axis aligned along the principal components u_k . An example of this coordinate system is shown in Figure 1, which, however, represents the case of empirical data. The following map assigns the new coordinates to a data point $x \in \mathcal{H}$:

$$\begin{cases} \mathcal{H} & \rightarrow \ell^2 \\ x & \mapsto (\langle u_k, x - E(X) \rangle)_{k=1}^{\infty}. \end{cases}$$

Dimension reduction is achieved by truncating after the first d coordinates. The idea is that these coordinates carry the most information as data points sampled from the distribution of X vary mostly around the first principle components. The ‘‘higher’’ coordinates are thus negligible. The subsequent encoding map is obtained:

$$\text{enc} : \begin{cases} \mathcal{H} & \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d \\ x & \mapsto (\langle u_k, x - E(X) \rangle)_{k=1}^d. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Given an encoding vector $(x_i)_{i=1}^d$, we can also define the corresponding decoding map:

$$\text{dec} : \begin{cases} \mathbb{R}^d & \rightarrow \mathcal{H} \\ (x_i)_{i=1}^d & \mapsto E(X) + \sum_{i=1}^d x_i u_i. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

It is now interesting to have a look at the reconstruction map $\text{rec} = \text{dec} \circ \text{enc}$ defined as

Figure 1: The new coordinate system of a normally distributed data sample.

the composition of encoding and decoding map. It is given by

$$\text{rec} : \begin{cases} \mathcal{H} & \rightarrow & \mathcal{H} \\ x & \mapsto & E(X) + \sum_{k=1}^d \langle u_k, x - E(X) \rangle u_k = E(X) + P_{\langle u_1, \dots, u_d \rangle}(x - E(X)), \end{cases}$$

where $P_{\langle u_1, \dots, u_d \rangle}$ denotes the orthogonal projection onto the subspace $\langle u_1, \dots, u_d \rangle$ spanned by the first d principal components. The attentive reader can now see: The reconstruction map is just the orthogonal projection onto the affine subspace $E(X) + \langle u_1, \dots, u_d \rangle$!

Remark 2.3. If the support of the distribution of X lies in a finite-dimensional hyperplane, then the sum in Equation 1 that constitutes the spectral decomposition of Σ will be finite. Therefore we can reconstruct the data sampled from this distribution perfectly if the dimension parameter d is chosen large enough (more on this later). In practice, however, noise is almost always present, so this assumption is only satisfied under ideal conditions.

2.1.2. Statistical Interpretation of PCA: Data Approximation through Affine Subspaces

In this section, we present another perspective on PCA, which involves finding the d -dimensional affine hyperplane that minimizes the so-called reconstruction error. This approach can be seen as a special case of manifold learning, where a d -dimensional linear manifold is “learned”.

First, we will briefly discuss affine subspaces, followed by an introduction to the reconstruction error of an affine subspace. Finally, we will show that minimizing the reconstruction error leads to the same optimal affine subspace found by optimizing for the directions of maximal variance.

Definition 2.4 (Affine subspaces). We call a subset $A \subseteq \mathcal{H}$ an *affine subspace* if it is of the form $A = p + V$, where $p \in \mathcal{H}$ and V is a linear subspace of \mathcal{H} . We denote by

$$\mathcal{A}_d := \{ p + V \mid p \in \mathcal{H} \text{ and } V \leq \mathcal{H} \text{ with } \dim(V) = d \}$$

the set of all d -dimensional subspaces.

Remark 2.5. Note that the linear subspace V that corresponds to an affine subspace $A = p + V$ is unique whereas the source point $p \in A$ can be replaced by any other point of the affine subspace.

Definition 2.6 (Projections on affine subspaces). Let $A = p + V$ be a closed affine subspace. The *orthogonal projection on A* is defined by the affine operator

$$P_A : \begin{cases} \mathcal{H} & \rightarrow & \mathcal{H} \\ x & \mapsto & p + P_V(x - p), \end{cases}$$

where P_V is the orthogonal projection on the closed linear subspace V .

Remark 2.7. The projection is independent of the source point of the affine subspace: If $A = p_1 + V = p_2 + V$, implying that $p_1 - p_2 \in V$, then

$$\begin{aligned} P_A(x) &= p_1 + P_V(x - p_1) = p_2 + (p_1 - p_2) + P_V(x - p_2) + \underbrace{P_V(p_2 - p_1)}_{=p_2-p_1} \\ &= p_2 + P_V(x - p_2). \end{aligned}$$

Note also that if A is not only an affine but a linear subspace, the orthogonal projection P_A coincides with the usual orthogonal projection on linear subspaces.

With this preliminary work, we are now ready to define the reconstruction error of a closed affine subspace. It is given by the expectation value of the squared Hilbert space norm between the data point and its orthogonal projection on that affine subspace.

Definition 2.8 (Reconstruction error). Let A be a closed affine subspace of \mathcal{H} . The *reconstruction error of A* is defined as

$$R(A) := E \left(\|X - P_A(X)\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \right).$$

We now want to optimize and find the d -dimensional affine subspace that minimizes the reconstruction error.

We consider the following optimization problem:

$$\text{Min}_{A \in \mathcal{A}_d} R(A). \quad (4)$$

The capitalized “Min” instead of “min” is just an abbreviated formal notation borrowed from mathematical optimization used to describe the optimization task as a whole without having clarified the existence of a minimum yet.

So the goal is to find the optimal affine subspace

$$A_{\text{opt}} \in \arg \min_{A \in \mathcal{A}_d} E \left(\|X - P_A(X)\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \right)$$

and to show that an optimal solution is given by $A_{\text{opt}} = E(X) + \langle u_1, \dots, u_d \rangle$. We will also discuss under which condition the solution is unique.

We will do so, by first simplifying the Minimization Problem 4 through a parallel shift of the affine subspace A such that it includes the expectation value $E(X)$. After that, we show that the reduced minimization problem is equivalent to a certain maximization problem involving the covariance operator Σ of X .

We start by providing Steiner’s theorem for Hilbert space valued random variables.

Lemma 2.9 (Steiner’s Theorem):

Let Y be a \mathcal{H} -valued random variable and $a \in \mathcal{H}$. Then, the expected squared error $E(\|Y - a\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2)$ decomposes as follows:

$$E \left(\|Y - a\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \right) = \text{Var}(Y) + \|E(Y) - a\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2,$$

where $\text{Var}(Y) := E(\|Y - E(Y)\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2)$ is the total variance of Y .

We thus have $E(\|Y - a\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2) \geq \text{Var}(Y)$ and the inequality is strict when $a \neq E(Y)$.

Proof. We calculate:

$$\begin{aligned} E \left(\|Y - a\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \right) &= E \left(\|(Y - E(Y)) + (E(Y) - a)\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \right) \\ &= E \left(\|Y - E(Y)\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \right) + \|E(Y) - a\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 + 2 \underbrace{\langle E(Y - E(Y)), E(Y) - a \rangle}_{=0}. \end{aligned}$$

□

This will help us now when we show, that affine subspaces that do not contain $E(X)$ can not be minimizers of the reconstruction error.

Lemma 2.10:

Let $A = p + V$ be a d -dimensional affine subspace, such that $E(X) \notin A$. Then the parallel shifted affine subspace $A_{\text{shift}} := E(X) + V$ has a smaller reconstruction error, i.e. $R(A_{\text{shift}}) < R(A)$.

Proof. We start by rewriting the reconstruction error of A :

$$\begin{aligned} R(A) &= E \left(\|X - P_A(X)\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \right) = E \left(\|(X - p) - P_V(X - p)\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \right) \\ &= E \left(\|(I - P_V)(X - p)\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \right). \end{aligned}$$

Now we can apply Steiner's Theorem 2.9 with $Y := (I - P_V)X$ and $a := (I - P_V)p$. The expectation value of Y is $E(Y) = (I - P_V)E(X)$. Now note that since $E(X) \notin p + V$, we have $E(X) - p \notin V$. Together with $\ker(I - P_V) = V$, this gives

$$(I - P_V)(E(X) - p) \neq 0.$$

That way, we see that $E(Y) \neq a$ and we obtain a strict inequality in Steiner's theorem:

$$\begin{aligned} R(A) &= E \left(\|(I - P_V)(X - p)\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \right) \\ &> E \left(\|(I - P_V)(X - E(X))\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \right) = R(A_{\text{shift}}). \end{aligned}$$

□

The above result tells us that we can restrict ourselves in the Minimization Problem 4 to the subset $\{A \in \mathcal{A}_d \mid E(X) \in A\} = \{E(X) + V \mid V \text{ is a } d\text{-dimensional subspace}\}$. So the problem finally boiled down to the minimization problem

$$\text{Min}_{V: \dim(V)=d} E \left(\|(I - P_V)(X - E(X))\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \right). \quad (5)$$

We will rewrite this in the next step and obtain an equivalent maximization problem that involves directly the covariance operator. From this formulation, we will see that minimizing the reconstruction error is equivalent to finding the subspace of biggest variance. We prepare ourselves with the following definition and lemma.

Definition 2.11 (Total variance). The *total variance* of the (square-integrable) random variable X is defined by

$$\text{Var}(X) := E \left(\|(X - E(X))\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \right).$$

For a closed subspace V , the *total variance of X along V* is given by the total variance of $P_V X$, that is,

$$\text{Var}(P_V X) = E \left(\|P_V(X - E(X))\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \right).$$

Lemma 2.12:

Let V be a closed subspace. The total variance along V is given by

$$\text{Var}(P_V X) = \text{tr}(P_V \Sigma).$$

Proof. We calculate:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Var}(P_V X) &= E\left(\|P_V(X - E(X))\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2\right) \\
&= E\left(\text{tr}(P_V |X - E(X)\rangle\langle X - E(X)|)\right) \\
&= \text{tr}(P_V E(|X - E(X)\rangle\langle X - E(X)|)) \\
&= \text{tr}(P_V \Sigma).
\end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 2.13:

The total variance can be expressed by $\text{Var}(X) = \text{tr}(\Sigma)$.

Proposition 2.14:

The Minimization Problem 5 is equivalent to the maximization problem

$$\text{Max}_{V: \dim(V)=d} \text{tr}(P_V \Sigma). \quad (6)$$

Proof. Let V be a d -dimensional linear subspace of \mathcal{H} . We use the Pythagorean theorem and Lemma 2.12 to obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
E\left(\|(I - P_V)(X - E(X))\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2\right) &= E\left(\|X - E(X)\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2\right) - E\left(\|P_V(X - E(X))\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2\right) \\
&= \text{Var}(X) - \text{tr}(P_V \Sigma) \\
&= \text{tr}(\Sigma) - \text{tr}(P_V \Sigma).
\end{aligned}$$

Since $\text{Var}(X)$ does not depend on the linear subspace V , we see directly that maximizing $\text{tr}(P_V \Sigma)$ over all d -dimensional linear subspaces minimizes the initial problem. □

The following theorem finally shows that the optimal affine subspace is, as announced, given by the eigenvectors to the largest eigenvalues of the covariance operator.

Theorem 2.15:

A solution to the Maximization Problem 6 is given by

$$\langle u_1, \dots, u_d \rangle \in \arg \max_{V: \dim(V)} \text{tr}(P_V \Sigma),$$

where the orthonormal system $(u_i)_{i=1}^d$ consists of the first vectors from the spectral decomposition of the covariance operator in Equation 1.

The resulting minimal reconstruction error is given by

$$R(A_{\text{opt}}) = \sum_{k=d+1}^{\infty} \sigma_k^2,$$

where $A_{\text{opt}} = E(X) + \langle u_1, \dots, u_d \rangle$.

Proof. Let V be d -dimensional linear subspace and $(v_l)_{l=1}^d$ an orthonormal basis of it. We use the spectral decomposition of $\Sigma = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sigma_k^2 |u_k\rangle \langle u_k|$ in order to rewrite

$$\mathrm{tr}(P_V \Sigma) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sigma_k^2 \mathrm{tr}(P_V |u_k\rangle \langle u_k|) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sigma_k^2 w_k, \quad (7)$$

where we introduced the “weights” $w_k := \mathrm{tr}(P_V |u_k\rangle \langle u_k|) = \sum_{l=1}^d |\langle v_l, u_k \rangle|^2$. They have the following properties:

1. the weights are non-negative and at most 1

$$0 \leq w_k = \sum_{l=1}^d |\langle v_l, u_k \rangle|^2 \leq \|u_k\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 = 1;$$

and

2. the total weight is bounded by d

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} w_k = \sum_{l=1}^d \underbrace{\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |\langle v_l, u_k \rangle|^2}_{\leq \|v_l\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 = 1} \leq d.$$

Here we used Parseval’s inequality in each property.

Under all weight sequences $(\tilde{w}_k)_{k=1}^{\infty}$ fulfilling the above two restrictions, we can obtain an upper bound in the expression $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sigma_k^2 w_k$ of Equation 7 if we packed the “total weight” onto the first d weights, i.e. setting $\tilde{w}_k := 1$ for $k = 1, \dots, d$ and $\tilde{w}_k := 0$ for $k \geq d + 1$. We get

$$\mathrm{tr}(P_V \Sigma) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sigma_k^2 w_k \leq \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sigma_k^2 \tilde{w}_k = \sum_{k=1}^d \sigma_k^2.$$

Let us now choose the subspace $V := \langle u_1, \dots, u_d \rangle$. We obtain:

$$\mathrm{tr}(P_{\langle u_1, \dots, u_d \rangle} \Sigma) = \mathrm{tr}\left(\sum_{k=1}^d \sigma_k^2 |u_k\rangle \langle u_k|\right) = \sum_{k=1}^d \sigma_k^2.$$

That shows, that $\langle u_1, \dots, u_d \rangle$ is indeed a solution.

The optimal reconstruction error is given by

$$R(A_{\mathrm{opt}}) = \mathrm{tr}(\Sigma) - \mathrm{tr}(P_V \Sigma) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sigma_k^2 - \sum_{k=1}^d \sigma_k^2 = \sum_{k=d+1}^{\infty} \sigma_k^2.$$

□

Short discussion of the uniqueness of the optimal subspace

Theorem 2.15 does not tell us anything about the uniqueness of the solution yet. It is worth noting that the spectral decomposition of Σ is itself not unique. To see that, let us investigate the descending sequence $(\sigma_k^2)_{k=1}^\infty \in \ell^1$ of eigenvalues of Σ . Since this sequence converges to 0, every positive eigenvalue is repeated only finitely many times. Renaming the sequence yields

$$\begin{aligned} & (\underbrace{\sigma_1^2, \dots, \sigma_{r_1}^2}_{=:\lambda_1}, \underbrace{\sigma_{r_1+1}^2, \dots, \sigma_{r_1+r_2}^2}_{=:\lambda_2}, \underbrace{\sigma_{r_1+r_2+1}^2, \dots, \sigma_{r_1+r_2+r_3}^2}_{=:\lambda_3}, \dots) \\ & = (\underbrace{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_1}_{r_1 \text{ times}}, \underbrace{\lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_2}_{r_2 \text{ times}}, \underbrace{\lambda_3, \dots, \lambda_3}_{r_3 \text{ times}}, \dots). \end{aligned}$$

Here r_l is the multiplicity of the l -th largest eigenvalue λ_l of Σ and the corresponding eigenspace is $U_l := \langle u_{r_1+\dots+r_{l-1}+1}, \dots, u_{r_1+\dots+r_l} \rangle$. We can rewrite the covariance operator:

$$\Sigma = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sigma_k^2 |u_k\rangle \langle u_k| = \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \lambda_l P_{U_l},$$

and see that way that the choice of the orthonormal basis of the eigenspaces is arbitrary and could have been chosen differently.

Now suppose that there exists a $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that the dimension parameter d fulfills

$$r_1 + \dots + r_{k-1} < d < r_1 + \dots + r_k.$$

According to Theorem 2.15 a solution is given by the orthogonal sum of $\bigoplus_{l=1}^{k-1} U_l$ and any $(d - \sum_{l=1}^{k-1} r_l)$ -dimensional subspace of U_k . Thus, the solution is not unique in this case. (In fact, all possible solutions have exactly this form.)

The only cases in which we can hope for a unique solution are thus those in which there is a strictly positive spectral gap between the eigenvalues σ_d^2 and σ_{d+1}^2 . This is exactly the content of the next proposition.

Proposition 2.16:

The solution of the Maximization Problem 6 is unique if and only if $\sigma_d^2 > \sigma_{d+1}^2$.

Proof. We have seen already, that $\sigma_d^2 > \sigma_{d+1}^2$ is a necessary condition for the uniqueness of the solution. We will show, that it also suffices.

Let $V \neq \langle u_1, \dots, u_d \rangle$ be a d -dimensional linear subspace. That implies, that there is a $v \in V$ and a $k \geq d+1$ such that $|\langle u_k, v \rangle|^2 > 0$, implying that also $w_k > 0$, where w_k is the weight on the k -th eigenvalue σ_k^2 , that was introduced in the proof of Theorem 2.15. This leads to a non-optimal weighting of the eigenvalues in Equation 7, since $\sigma_k^2 < \sigma_d^2$. Thus the subspace V cannot be optimal. \square

2.2. The Sample Picture

So far we have assumed that we know the exact distribution of X . However, this is almost never the case in applications. What can we do in such a case?

Suppose we have a sequence of n \mathcal{H} -valued observations X_1, \dots, X_n that are distributed independently and identically. As we do not know the exact distribution of the data, we resort to a data-driven approach. We replace the unknown distribution of X with the observed empirical distribution defined as

$$P_n := \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \delta_{X_k}.$$

With this solution, we can obtain the same results as from the section on the population picture by simply replacing the population distribution with the empirical distribution P_n . We summarize the most important ones here.

The expectation value of X under the empirical measure is given by

$$E_{X \sim P_n}(X) = \bar{X}_n := \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n X_k,$$

and the empirical covariance operator is given by

$$\hat{\Sigma}_n := E_{X \sim P_n}(|X - E_{X \sim P_n}(X)\rangle \langle X - E_{X \sim P_n}(X)|) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n |X_k - \bar{X}_n\rangle \langle X_k - \bar{X}_n|.$$

Remark 2.17. Note that the empirical covariance operator defined here differs from the also commonly encountered unbiased estimator $\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{k=1}^n |X_k - \bar{X}_n\rangle \langle X_k - \bar{X}_n|$ of Σ by a prefactor. The prefactor does not matter for our purpose, since a rescaling does only affect the size of the eigenvalues in the spectral decomposition of $\hat{\Sigma}_n$, not the eigenvectors.

From the representation of $\hat{\Sigma}_n$, we can see directly that the image lies in the space spanned by the vectors $X_1 - \bar{X}_n, \dots, X_n - \bar{X}_n$. Note that these are linearly dependent as they sum to zero:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n (X_k - \bar{X}_n) = \sum_{k=1}^n X_k - n\bar{X}_n = 0.$$

This observation culminates in

Lemma 2.18:

The rank of $\hat{\Sigma}_n$ is at most $n - 1$.

For this reason, the spectral decomposition of the empirical covariance operator can be simplified as there can be at most $n - 1$ non-zero eigenvalues:

$$\hat{\Sigma}_n = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \hat{\sigma}_k^2 |\hat{u}_k\rangle \langle \hat{u}_k|. \quad (8)$$

This also shows us that it does not make sense to choose the dimension parameter d larger than $n - 1$ in practice.

The encoding and decoding map defined in 2 and 3 are given the same way, except that the principal components u_k are estimated by its empirical version \hat{u}_k and the exact expectation value $E(X)$ is estimated by \bar{X}_n . More explicitly, we get:

$$\widehat{\text{enc}}_n : \begin{cases} \mathcal{H} & \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d \\ x & \mapsto \left(\langle \hat{u}_k, x - \bar{X}_n \rangle \right)_{k=1}^d \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

and

$$\widehat{\text{dec}}_n : \begin{cases} \mathbb{R}^d & \rightarrow \mathcal{H} \\ (x_i)_{i=1}^d & \mapsto \bar{X}_n + \sum_{i=1}^d x_i \hat{u}_i. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The affine subspace $\hat{A}_{\text{opt}} := \bar{X}_n + \langle \hat{u}_1, \dots, \hat{u}_d \rangle$ onto which we orthogonally project minimizes the empirical reconstruction error

$$R_n(A) := E_{X \sim P_n} \left(\|X - P_A X\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \right) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \|X_k - P_A X_k\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2.$$

The optimal reconstruction error is thus given by $R_n(\hat{A}_{\text{opt}}) = \sum_{k=d+1}^{n-1} \hat{\sigma}_k^2$ (Theorem 2.15) and \hat{A}_{opt} is a unique solution of the empirical reconstruction error minimization if and only if $\hat{\sigma}_d^2 > \hat{\sigma}_{d+1}^2$ (Proposition 2.16).

The affine subspace \hat{A}_{opt} is only an estimation of the theoretical but unfeasible optimal subspace A_{opt} and has thus a higher reconstruction error. The amount by which the reconstruction error exceeds the optimal reconstruction error is called the excess risk.

Definition 2.19 (Excess risk). The *excess risk* $\mathcal{E}(A)$ of a closed affine subspace A is defined via

$$\mathcal{E}(A) := R(A) - R(A_{\text{opt}}).$$

In this context, it is certainly interesting to study conditions under which we obtain upper bounds on the excess risk to assess the quality of the estimate. This was done, for example, in [RW20].

2.3. Calculation of PCA

So far we have worked with covariance operators on Hilbert spaces and their spectral decomposition.

If the Hilbert space at hand is finite-dimensional, i.e. up to an isomorphism a version of

\mathbb{R}^p , this is usually not a problem. In infinite-dimensional Hilbert spaces, on the other hand, the spectral decomposition can be computed explicitly only in special cases and is not suitable for an algorithmic treatment.

We will show how we can circumvent this problem. The presented method is based on the singular value decomposition and can be also useful and computationally more efficient in finite-dimensional Hilbert spaces when the dimension p is much higher than the number of data points n .

To do so, we decompose the empirical covariance operator $\hat{\Sigma}_n$ into the linear operators

$$L_n : \begin{cases} \mathcal{H} & \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\text{emp}}^n \\ x & \mapsto (\langle X_k - \bar{X}_n | x \rangle)_{k=1}^n \end{cases}$$

and

$$L_n^* : \begin{cases} \mathbb{R}_{\text{emp}}^n & \rightarrow \mathcal{H} \\ v & \mapsto \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n v_k (X_k - \bar{X}_n). \end{cases}$$

Here, $\mathbb{R}_{\text{emp}}^n$ is simply the ordinary \mathbb{R}^n , which, however, has been equipped with the empirical scalar product $\langle v | w \rangle_{\mathbb{R}_{\text{emp}}^n} := \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n v_k w_k$ instead of the standard scalar product. The suffix “emp” stresses this fact.

The notation we have chosen already suggests that L_n^* is the adjoint operator of L_n . The following lemma confirms this.

Lemma 2.20:

The linear operator $L_n^ \in L(\mathbb{R}_{\text{emp}}^n, \mathcal{H})$ is indeed the adjoint operator of $L_n \in L(\mathcal{H}, \mathbb{R}_{\text{emp}}^n)$.*

Proof. Let $v \in \mathbb{R}_{\text{emp}}^n$ and $u \in \mathcal{H}$. We get:

$$\langle v | L_n u \rangle_{\mathbb{R}_{\text{emp}}^n} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n v_k \langle X_k - \bar{X}_n | u \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} = \left\langle \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n v_k (X_k - \bar{X}_n) \middle| u \right\rangle_{\mathcal{H}} = \langle L_n^* v | u \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}.$$

□

The empirical covariance operator can now be written as $\hat{\Sigma}_n = L_n^* L_n$. The idea is to apply Lemma A.3 and analyze the operator $K_n^{\text{cen}} := L_n L_n^* \in L(\mathbb{R}_{\text{emp}}^n)$ instead, where the positions of L_n and L_n^* have been swapped.

The operator is given by the n -dimensional normed Gram matrix of the centered data points $Z_i := X_i - \bar{X}_n$, $i = 1, \dots, n$:

$$K_n^{\text{cen}} = \frac{1}{n} \begin{pmatrix} \langle Z_1 | Z_1 \rangle & \langle Z_1 | Z_2 \rangle & \cdots & \langle Z_1 | Z_n \rangle \\ \langle Z_2 | Z_1 \rangle & \langle Z_2 | Z_2 \rangle & \cdots & \langle Z_2 | Z_n \rangle \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \langle Z_n | Z_1 \rangle & \langle Z_n | Z_2 \rangle & \cdots & \langle Z_n | Z_n \rangle \end{pmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

(Here we abused slightly the notation and named the matrix representation regarding the standard basis the same way as the underlying operator.)

Remark 2.21. Alternatively, we can introduce the (uncentered) normed Gram Matrix of the data points $K_n := \frac{1}{n}(\langle X_i | X_j \rangle)_{ij}$ and the orthogonal projector $P_{\langle 1_n \rangle^\perp} = I - |1_n\rangle \langle 1_n| \in L(\mathbb{R}_{\text{emp}}^n)$ (where $1_n := (1, \dots, 1)^T \in \mathbb{R}^n$) with matrix representation $I_n - \frac{1}{n}1_n 1_n^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ to see $K_n^{\text{cen}} = P_{\langle 1_n \rangle^\perp} K_n P_{\langle 1_n \rangle^\perp}$ as operators or matrices respectively.

We can now compute the eigenpairs of K_n^{cen} in order to obtain the spectral decomposition

$$K_n^{\text{cen}} = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \hat{\sigma}_k^2 |v_k\rangle \langle v_k|.$$

Due to Lemma A.2, the operator has the same eigenvalues as $\hat{\Sigma}_n$. This is also the reason why the sum has only $n-1$ summands (Note also that $1_n \in \ker(L_n^*) \subseteq \ker(K_n)$, which can be also seen from Remark 2.21). Keep here also in mind that the eigenvectors $v_k \in \mathbb{R}_{\text{emp}}^n$ are normed with respect to the empirical norm.

Once we have the spectral decomposition, it is fairly easy to specify the empirical principal components.

Proposition 2.22:

The empirical principal components are given by

$$\hat{u}_k = \frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}_k} L_n^* v_k = \frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}_k} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (v_k)_i (X_i - \bar{X}_n)$$

for all indices $k \in \{1, \dots, n-1\}$ with a strictly positive eigenvalue $\hat{\sigma}_k^2 > 0$.

Proof. Just apply Lemma A.3 to the operator L_n^* . □

In the practical application of PCA, we are interested in the new coordinates of the data points X_i given by the empirical encoding map $\widehat{\text{enc}}_n(X_i)$. It turns out that these coordinates can be calculated surprisingly simply in terms of the eigenpairs of K_n^{cen} .

Proposition 2.23:

The encoding map of the i -th data point X_i is given by $\widehat{\text{enc}}_n(X_i) = (\hat{\sigma}_j (v_j)_i)_{j=1}^d$. Saying it differently, we can write down the matrix

$$\left(\begin{array}{c|c|c|c} | & | & & | \\ \hat{\sigma}_1 v_1 & \hat{\sigma}_2 v_2 & \dots & \hat{\sigma}_d v_d \\ | & | & & | \end{array} \right) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$$

and read off the new coordinates of the data points as the rows of the matrix.

Proof. The j -th encoded coordinate of the datapoint X_i is given by

$$\begin{aligned}\widehat{\text{enc}}_n(X_i)_j &= \langle \hat{u}_j | X_i - \bar{X}_n \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} = \frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}_j} \langle L_n^* v_j | \underbrace{X_i - \bar{X}_n}_{=L_n^* e_i} \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} \\ &= \frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}_j} \langle \underbrace{K_n^{\text{cen}} v_j}_{=\hat{\sigma}_j^2 v_j} | e_i \rangle_{\mathbb{R}_{\text{emp}}^n} = \hat{\sigma}_j(v_j)_i.\end{aligned}$$

□

2.4. Choice of the Dimension Parameter d

So far we have taken the dimensional parameter d as given. Here we want to briefly address the question of how d can be selected appropriately for the respective application and present the most common methods. This overview is inspired by [LV07, p.30] and [Mur22, Section 20.1.4, p.658-660].

The easiest case is when we want to use PCA for visualization of high dimensional data, where we typically set d to 2 or 3 (and in rare cases maybe even to 1).

Otherwise, it is certainly desirable that the subspace we project on explains most of the total variance in the data. To cast this into formulas, we set a to a certain degree arbitrary threshold $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ (typical choices are $\alpha = 0.9$ or $\alpha = 0.95$) and choose d as the minimal integer fulfilling

$$\frac{\sum_{l=1}^d \hat{\sigma}_l^2}{\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \hat{\sigma}_k^2} = \frac{\sum_{l=1}^d \hat{\sigma}_l^2}{\text{tr}(\hat{\Sigma}_n)} \geq \alpha. \quad (12)$$

It is worth mentioning that there are similar approaches that work with individual variances instead of cumulative ones. For example, one could discard all components having a variance lower than 1% of the total one.

Lastly, let us adopt the viewpoint of PCA being a linear manifold learning method, finding the in some sense best affine hyperplane describing the data. Suppose that the support of the distribution of the data lies within a d -dimensional hyperplane. We had then $\text{rank}(\Sigma) = d$ and with high enough sample size also $\text{rank}(\hat{\Sigma}_n) = \text{rank}(K_n^{\text{cen}}) = d$. The number of nonzero eigenvalues would be then the estimate of the *intrinsic dimension* d of the data.

However, this is just an ideal scenario since in practice we almost always encounter noise. If we assume though that this noise is negligible in comparison to the variance along the d -th principal component of the data, we would see a visible gap when we plot the descendingly ordered eigenvalues. This way, we simply can estimate d visually.

Unfortunately, this will not be always the case: imagine, for example, that the intrinsic dimension d is itself very large. It could then be that the variance along the d -th principal

component is of the same order of magnitude as the noise. This makes it impossible to distinguish the noise from the intrinsic variance. The approach described by 12 is then also in this case a reasonable method to handle this problem.

3. Kernel Principal Component Analysis

3.1. Introduction to Kernel-Based Learning

In machine learning, so-called kernel methods are algorithms used for pattern analysis. They enable us to implicitly embed data into a high-dimensional linear space, allowing the application of well-understood and simple linear algorithms. Despite the simplicity of these algorithms, the nonlinearity of the embedding results in complex outcomes. The following introductory example should shed some light on this and exemplify the ideas behind kernel methods.

Suppose that we observe n labeled data points X_1, \dots, X_n in the sample space $\mathcal{X} := \mathbb{R}^2$ along with their binary labels $Y_1, \dots, Y_n \in \{-1, 1\}$. Our objective is to classify new, unlabeled data points based on the current observations. Imagine we are given a picture similar to Figure 2.

Figure 2: The data points are linearly separable.

Clearly, the data points can be separated linearly by a $(d - 1)$ -dimensional hyperplane (which is a straight line in 2D). It is the idea of support vector machines (SVMs) to identify the hyperplane that achieves the highest separation between the two classes, by maximizing the distance between the nearest data point on each side of the hyperplane. The decision boundary, as shown in Figure 2, is used for classification of new unclassified data points. A red or blue label is assigned to them depending on which side of the hyperplane they appear.

But what can we do if the situation looks as in Figure 3?

Clearly, the linear SVM approach does not work here. A way out is to embed the data points from the sample space \mathcal{X} into a higher-dimensional feature space \mathcal{H} via the feature

Figure 3: The data points can not be separated linearly.

map

$$\phi : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}.$$

The hope is now that an appropriately chosen feature map ϕ will enable us to separate linearly the embedded data points $\phi(X_1), \dots, \phi(X_n)$ in the feature space \mathcal{H} by a hyperplane.

Let us illustrate that with the following, for now arbitrary-looking feature map:

$$\phi : \begin{cases} \mathbb{R}^2 & \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3 \\ (x_1, x_2) & \mapsto (x_1^2, x_2^2, \sqrt{2}x_1x_2). \end{cases}$$

The embedded data is visualized in Figure 4 and it is clear that it is linearly separable in \mathcal{H} .

We can then pull back the linear decision boundary in the feature space to the sample space via ϕ , which finally gives us the depicted decision boundary in Figure 3.

Not only have we achieved our goal of finding an appropriate nonlinear classification boundary. Behind the scenes, the SVM algorithm only depends on the scalar product between two points $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$ in feature space. In our toy example, it is given by

$$k(x, y) := \langle \phi(x) | \phi(y) \rangle_{\mathbb{R}^3} = \langle x | y \rangle_{\mathbb{R}^2}^2.$$

This is our first example of a kernel. It is known under the name polynomial kernel of order 2.

We can thus avoid computing the embedded data points $\phi(X_1), \dots, \phi(X_n)$ explicitly. Especially for very high-dimensional feature maps it is computationally more efficient only to compute the $\frac{n(n+1)}{2}$ different scalar products $k(X_i, X_j)_{i \leq j}$.

Figure 4: The embedded data via the feature map ϕ .

Let us give a formal definition of kernels over a sample space \mathcal{X} . In the context of kernel learning a sample space \mathcal{X} is just a set without the necessity of any further structure.

Definition 3.1 (Kernels). A real-valued function $k : \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called a (*real*) *kernel over \mathcal{X}* if there exists a Hilbert space \mathcal{H} and a map $\phi : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$, such that

$$k(x, y) = \langle \phi(x) | \phi(y) \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}$$

for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$.

A kernel has the following characteristic properties.

Proposition 3.2:

Let k be a kernel over \mathcal{X} . Then:

1. k is symmetric, that is $k(x, y) = k(y, x)$ for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$.
2. k is positive semidefinite. That is, for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and data samples $S = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ of length n , the kernel matrix $K(S) := (k(x_i, x_j))_{i,j=1}^n$ is positive semidefinite.

Proof. The first property is a direct consequence of the symmetry of scalar products. For the second property let $S = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ be an arbitrary data sample of length n and

$\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^n$. We use the fact, that $k = \langle \phi(\cdot) | \phi(\cdot) \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}$ for some feature map $\phi : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$:

$$\alpha^T K(S) \alpha = \sum_{i,j=1}^n \langle \phi(x_i), \phi(x_j) \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} \alpha_i \alpha_j = \left\| \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i \phi(x_i) \right\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \geq 0.$$

□

An interesting question we can ask ourselves is the following: Under which conditions is a function $k : \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a kernel over \mathcal{X} ?

Surprisingly, the two properties mentioned in Proposition 3.2 are already sufficient for this. The following deep theorem was first mentioned by NACHMAN ARONSAJN in his main contribution to the theory of reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces [Aro50, p. 344] and there essentially attributed to ELIAKIM HASTINGS MOORE.

Theorem 3.3 (Moore-Aronszajn Theorem (version 1), [SC08, Theorem 4.16, p. 118]): *A function $k : \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a kernel over \mathcal{X} if and only if it is symmetric and positive semidefinite.*

Generally, it is a hard problem to come up with an appropriate feature map ϕ . The above Theorem 3.3 tells us that we just need to come up with a kernel function k , characterized by its symmetry and positive semidefiniteness, and get the feature map implicitly for free when the algorithm just depends on the scalar product of the embedded data points in feature space. This is known as the *kernel trick*.

Remark 3.4 (The kernel trick, [SS02, Remark 2.8, p. 34]). Given an algorithm that is formulated in terms of a scalar product, one can construct an alternative algorithm by replacing the scalar product with a kernel k .

In practice, we can simply try out different kernels. There is a variety of kernels to choose from and there are many possible ways to construct and combine new kernels from old ones.

Note that the PCA algorithm described in Section 2.3 is solely dependent on scalar products (see also Remark 2.21). Therefore, the algorithm can be kernelized to create the Kernel PCA (KPCA) algorithm.

However, before delving into KPCA, we will establish the Moore-Aronszajn Theorem 3.3 in the upcoming section. This theorem is proven using the theory of reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces, which are specialized Hilbert spaces of functions $f : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ that are the natural feature spaces corresponding to a kernel k . In the next section, we will examine the for our purposes most important properties of these spaces and also introduce the to a kernel associated integral operator, which is deeply connected to the covariance operator in KPCA.

3.2. The Theory of Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Spaces

3.2.1. Introduction to Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Spaces

In this introduction about reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces we mainly follow the exposition in [PR16, Chapter 1 and 2]. We start by providing the formal definition.

Definition 3.5 (Reproducing kernel Hilbert space, [PR16, Definition 1.1 p. 3-4]). Let $\mathcal{X} \neq \emptyset$ and \mathcal{H} be a real Hilbert function space, i.e. a real Hilbert space consisting of real-valued functions defined on \mathcal{X} . Then \mathcal{H} is called *reproducing kernel Hilbert space* if the evaluation functionals

$$\delta_x : \begin{cases} \mathcal{H} & \rightarrow & \mathbb{R} \\ f & \mapsto & f(x) \end{cases}$$

are continuous for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$.

The Riesz representation theorem (see for example [Wer18, Theorem V.3.6, p. 246]) tells us that the evaluation functional δ_x can be represented by an element $k_x \in \mathcal{H}$, i.e. $\delta_x = \langle k_x | \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}$. With that in mind, we can define the so-called *reproducing kernel* of a reproducing kernel Hilbert space.

Definition 3.6 (Reproducing kernel, [PR16, Definition 1.2, p. 4]). Let \mathcal{H} be a reproducing kernel Hilbert space over \mathcal{X} . The *reproducing kernel* of \mathcal{H} is defined as

$$k(x, y) := \langle k_x | k_y \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}$$

for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$.

The following simple proposition explains the naming of reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces and its reproducing kernels. In fact, many introductions to the subject take the properties formulated in it as the starting point for defining reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces.

Proposition 3.7:

Let \mathcal{H} be a reproducing kernel Hilbert space with corresponding reproducing kernel k . Then:

1. we have $k(\cdot, x) \in \mathcal{H}$ for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$; and
2. the **reproducing property** $f(x) = \langle k(\cdot, x) | f \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}$ holds for all $f \in \mathcal{H}$ and $x \in \mathcal{X}$.

Proof. Both properties are direct consequences of the fact that $k_x = k(\cdot, x)$ and that k_x is the Riesz representation of the evaluation functional δ_x . We can see the former via

$$k_x(y) = \delta_y(k_x) = \langle k_y, k_x \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} = k(y, x).$$

□

Our next goal is to show that different reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces also yield different reproducing kernels. This is the subject of Proposition 3.9. Before that, we show the following auxiliary lemma, which is interesting in itself.

Lemma 3.8 ([PR16, Proposition 2.1, p. 17]):

The subspace $\langle k_x | x \in \mathcal{X} \rangle$ is dense in the reproducing kernel Hilbert space \mathcal{H} .

Proof. Let $f \in \langle k_x | x \in \mathcal{X} \rangle^{\perp} \subseteq \mathcal{H}$. Then $f(x) = \langle k_x | f \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} = 0$, meaning that $\langle k_x | x \in \mathcal{X} \rangle^{\perp} = \{0\}$. The denseness follows from this (see [Wer18, Korollar V.3.5, p. 246]). □

Proposition 3.9 ([PR16, Proposition 2.3, p. 18]):

Let \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2 be two reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces over \mathcal{X} with the same reproducing kernel $k : \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Then $\mathcal{H}_1 = \mathcal{H}_2$ as Hilbert spaces.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{H}_{\text{pre}} := \langle k(\cdot, x) | x \in \mathcal{X} \rangle$. We know from Lemma 3.8 that \mathcal{H}_{pre} is a dense subspace of both \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2 .

Now let $f = \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i k_{x_i}$ and $g = \sum_{j=1}^n \beta_j k_{y_j}$. We obtain:

$$\langle f | g \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_1} = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_i \beta_j \underbrace{\langle k_{x_i} | k_{y_j} \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_1}}_{=k(x_i, y_j)} = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_i \beta_j \langle k_{x_i} | k_{y_j} \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_2} = \langle f | g \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_2}.$$

That is, the scalar products and especially also the norms agree on \mathcal{H}_{pre} .

Now consider $f \in \mathcal{H}_1$. By density, there is a sequence $(f_n) \in (\mathcal{H}_{\text{pre}})^{\mathbb{N}}$ with $\|f - f_n\|_{\mathcal{H}_1} \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 0$. Then (f_n) is a Cauchy sequence in \mathcal{H}_1 and thus also a Cauchy sequence in \mathcal{H}_2 , which implies the existence of a $g \in \mathcal{H}_2$ with $\|g - f_n\|_{\mathcal{H}_2} \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 0$ by the completeness of \mathcal{H}_2 .

Note that the evaluation functionals are continuous on reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces by definition. In other words: norm convergence does also imply pointwise convergence. Thus, $f(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) = g(x)$ for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$. This shows $\mathcal{H}_1 \subseteq \mathcal{H}_2$ and by interchanging roles also $\mathcal{H}_1 = \mathcal{H}_2$ as sets.

It can also be easily seen that the scalar product agrees on \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2 since it is continuous and agrees on the dense subspace \mathcal{H}_{pre} (see [AE08, Theorem 2.1, p. 10]). This shows that the two Hilbert spaces are the same. \square

When k is a reproducing kernel, the preceding proposition justifies the notation \mathcal{H}_k for the associated unique RKHS. We will always use this notation in the future.

The next proposition introduces the canonical feature map of a reproducing kernel Hilbert space.

Proposition 3.10 ([SC08, Lemma 4.19, p. 120]):

A reproducing kernel k is also a kernel as defined in Definition 3.1. The canonical feature map is given by

$$\phi_k : \begin{cases} \mathcal{X} & \rightarrow & \mathcal{H}_k \\ x & \mapsto & k_x. \end{cases}$$

Proof. We indeed have $\langle \phi_k(x) | \phi_k(y) \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_k} = \langle k_x | k_y \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_k} = k(x, y)$. \square

Corollary 3.11:

A reproducing kernel $k : \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a symmetric and positive semidefinite function.

Proof. Follows directly from Proposition 3.2. \square

A natural question to ask at this point is: Is a symmetric and positive semidefinite function also a reproducing kernel, that is, is there a corresponding reproducing kernel Hilbert space? The answer to that is yes. The below theorem is another version of the Moore-Aronszajn theorem. We will sketch the construction of the corresponding RKHS.

Theorem 3.12 (Moore-Aronszajn Theorem (version 2), [PR16, Theorem 2.14, p. 25]): *Let $k : \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be symmetric and positive semidefinite. Then k is a reproducing kernel, i.e. there is a reproducing kernel Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_k such that k is the corresponding reproducing kernel.*

The proof idea is based on the properties in Proposition 3.7. We need to ensure that $k(\cdot, x) \in \mathcal{H}_k$ for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$ and that the reproducing property is fulfilled. Therefore we start with the space spanned by the $k(\cdot, x)$. The reproducing property will then determine the scalar product on this space. The inner product space constructed in this way then only needs to be completed.

Sketch of proof of Theorem 3.12. We define $\mathcal{H}_{\text{pre}} := \langle k(\cdot, x) | x \in \mathcal{X} \rangle \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{X}}$ and denote as usual $k_x := k(\cdot, x)$. In order to define an inner product, we keep in mind that the reproducing property has to be fulfilled, i.e. $\langle k_x | k_y \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_{\text{pre}}} := k_y(x) = k(x, y)$. We extend this definition linearly. For $f = \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i k_{x_i}$ and $g = \sum_{j=1}^n \beta_j k_{y_j}$ we obtain then the definition

$$\langle f | g \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_{\text{pre}}} := \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_i \beta_j k(x_i, y_j).$$

It turns out that the above definition is independent of the particular sum representation of the functions in \mathcal{H}_{pre} .

We need to show now that the above-defined bilinear form $\langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_{\text{pre}}}$ is indeed a scalar product. This is where the properties of k enter. The symmetricity and positive semidefiniteness are directly inherited from the corresponding properties of k . The strict positive definiteness can then be shown by using a generalization of the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality for symmetric, positive semidefinite bilinear forms and the reproducing property.

The inner product space constructed in this way can now be completed. Note that a Cauchy sequence $(f_n) \in \mathcal{H}_{\text{pre}}^{\mathbb{N}}$ is also a pointwise Cauchy sequence because of the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality and reproducing property:

$$|f_n(x) - f_m(x)| = \langle k_x | f_n - f_m \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_{\text{pre}}} \leq \|k_x\|_{\mathcal{H}_{\text{pre}}} \|f_n - f_m\|_{\mathcal{H}_{\text{pre}}} \xrightarrow{n, m \rightarrow \infty} 0.$$

We now define \mathcal{H}_k as the set of pointwise limits of Cauchy sequences of \mathcal{H}_{pre} , extend the scalar product on this space, and verify that this is indeed a reproducing kernel Hilbert space with reproducing kernel k .

We have left out most technical details to focus more on the core idea. For full proofs

see for example [PR16, Theorem 2.14, p. 25], [SC08, Theorem 4.16, p. 118] or [SC04, Theorem 3.11, p. 61]. \square

So, overall, we see that the initial distinction between reproducing kernels, kernels, and symmetric positive semidefinite functions is only an artificial one.

Corollary 3.13:

Let $k : \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Then the following statements are equivalent:

1. k is a reproducing kernel coming from an RKHS (see Definition 3.6);
2. k is a kernel (as defined in 3.1); and
3. k is a symmetric and positive semidefinite function.

From now on, we will therefore no longer distinguish between the three terms and will simply call them kernels.

Another main statement that follows from Proposition 3.9 and the Moore-Aronszajn Theorem 3.12 is the following.

Corollary 3.14:

There is a one-to-one correspondence between kernels and reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces.

3.2.2. Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Spaces as Canonical Feature Spaces

So far we have seen that each kernel k has an associated RKHS \mathcal{H}_k and that the canonical feature map in it is given by $\mathcal{X} \ni x \mapsto k_x \in \mathcal{H}_k$. However, there may be different feature spaces (that is, Hilbert spaces) with feature maps ϕ leading to the same kernel k . The following theorem shows that the RKHS \mathcal{H}_k is in a sense the minimal feature space. From any other feature space, there is a canonical metric surjection into the RKHS \mathcal{H}_k of the kernel k .

The following theorem is inspired by a partial statement in [SC08, Theorem 4.21, p. 121]. However, the proof is new and has been developed in the context of this master thesis.

Theorem 3.15:

Let $k : \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a kernel and let $\phi : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ be a feature map into the feature Hilbert space \mathcal{H} leading to the kernel k , meaning that $k = \langle \phi(\cdot) | \phi(\cdot) \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}$. Then, there is a canonical metric surjection from the feature Hilbert space \mathcal{H} into the RKHS \mathcal{H}_k , given by:

$$V : \begin{cases} \mathcal{H} & \rightarrow & \mathcal{H}_k \\ w & \mapsto & \langle \phi(\cdot) | w \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}. \end{cases}$$

Proof. We start by defining V on the subspace $\langle \phi(\mathcal{X}) \rangle$ only. For $w = \phi(x)$, we obtain

$$V(w) = V(\phi(x)) = \langle \phi(\cdot) | \phi(x) \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} = k(\cdot, x) = k_x \in \mathcal{H}_k$$

and thus $\|V(w)\|_{\mathcal{H}_k}^2 = \|k_x\|_{\mathcal{H}_k}^2 = k(x, x) = \langle \phi(x) | \phi(x) \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} = \|w\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$.

We can extend this linearly to $\langle \phi(\mathcal{X}) \rangle$ and check that the operator V obtained in this way is an isometric isomorphism between the two pre-Hilbert spaces $\langle \phi(\mathcal{X}) \rangle \subseteq \mathcal{H}$ and $\langle k_x | x \in \mathcal{X} \rangle \subseteq \mathcal{H}_k$. By completion, we are extending V to an isomorphism between $U := \overline{\langle \phi(\mathcal{X}) \rangle}$ and \mathcal{H}_k (Remember that $\langle k_x | x \in \mathcal{X} \rangle$ is dense in \mathcal{H}_k by Lemma 3.8).

Let $w \in U$, $(w_n) \in (\langle \phi(\mathcal{X}) \rangle)^{\mathbb{N}}$ with $\|w_n - w\|_{\mathcal{H}} \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 0$ and $x \in \mathcal{X}$. We calculate:

$$V(w)(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} V(w_n)(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle \phi(x) | w_n \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} = \langle \phi(x) | w \rangle_{\mathcal{H}},$$

that is, $V(w) = \langle \phi(\cdot) | w \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}$ as stated in the theorem.

Finally, let $w_{\perp} \in U^{\perp} \subseteq \phi(\mathcal{X})^{\perp}$. We have by definition $\langle \phi(\cdot) | w_{\perp} \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} = 0$. That shows, that we can define V on the whole Hilbert space as stated by decomposing $w = w_{\parallel} + w_{\perp} \in \mathcal{H} = U \oplus U^{\perp}$.

To sum it up in other words: the canonical metric surjection V consists of an orthogonal projection from V onto U composed with the Hilbert space isomorphism between U and \mathcal{H}_k discussed above. \square

Remark 3.16. Note that the decision boundaries in support vector classification are of the form $\{x \in \mathcal{X} \mid \langle \phi(x) | w \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} = b\} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$. Theorem 3.15 therefore tells us that all possible classification boundaries are determined by the level sets of the functions in the RKHS \mathcal{H}_k . When selecting a suitable kernel k , this fact should be taken into account.

3.2.3. The Associated Integral Operator

We will introduce here the integral operator associated with kernels that fulfill certain conditions. We will see later that these are closely related to the covariance operator in Kernel PCA.

We start by defining what it means for a kernel to be p -integrable. We will see that a p -integrable kernel results in the associated RKHS consisting of L^p functions.

Definition 3.17 (p -integrable kernel, [SC08, Theorem 4.26, p. 126]). Let $p \in [1, \infty)$ and \mathcal{X} be a measurable space equipped with a probability measure P on it. Further, let k be a measurable kernel on \mathcal{X} (see Definition B.1). The kernel k is called p -integrable (with respect to P) if the corresponding RKHS \mathcal{H}_k is separable and

$$\|k\|_{L^p(P)} := \left(\int_{\mathcal{X}} k^{\frac{p}{2}}(x, x) P(dx) \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} = \left(\int_{\mathcal{X}} \|k_x\|_{\mathcal{H}_k}^p P(dx) \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} = \|\phi_k\|_{L^p(P; \mathcal{H}_k)} < \infty,$$

that is, if the canonical feature map $\phi_k : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_k$, $x \mapsto k_x$ is in the Bochner-Lebesgue space $L^p(P; \mathcal{H}_k)$.

Remark 3.18. The strange-looking condition requiring the separability of \mathcal{H}_k is crucial here. It ensures the measurability of the canonical feature map ϕ_k and of the function $\mathcal{X} \ni x \mapsto k(x, x) \in \mathbb{R}$ (see Lemma B.3 and the reference given there).

As demonstrated in Lemma B.5 of the appendix, this condition is generally met for a broad range of kernels prevalent in practical applications, namely those that are continuous on separable topological spaces.

Proposition 3.19 (Embedding operator into $L^p(P)$, [SC08, Theorem 4.26, p. 126]):
Let $p \in [1, \infty)$ and k be an p -integrable kernel in the measurable space \mathcal{X} equipped with probability measure P . Then the corresponding RKHS \mathcal{H}_k consists of p -integrable functions and the embedding operator

$$J : \begin{cases} \mathcal{H}_k & \rightarrow & L^p(P) \\ f & \mapsto & f \end{cases}$$

is bounded with $\|J\| \leq \|k\|_{L^p(P)}$.

Proof. First, Lemma B.2 from the appendix shows that the functions in \mathcal{H}_k are measurable. Now let $f \in \mathcal{H}_k$. We obtain

$$\int_{\mathcal{X}} |f(x)|^p P(dx) = \int_{\mathcal{X}} |\langle k_x | f \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_k}|^p P(dx) \leq \int_{\mathcal{X}} \|k_x\|_{\mathcal{H}_k}^p P(dx) \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}_k}^p = \|k\|_{L^p(P)}^p \|f\|_{\mathcal{H}_k}^p,$$

which shows the statement. \square

Remark 3.20. Contrary to what the name embedding operator suggests, J is not necessarily injective. For example, consider the case where P is an empirical measure.

We will be interested only in the case $p = 2$, since here we can use the Hilbert space structure of $L^2(P)$. The next proposition introduces the adjoint operator of the embedding operator.

Proposition 3.21 (Adjoint of embedding operator, [SC08, Theorem 4.26, p. 126]):
The adjoint operator of the embedding operator $J : \mathcal{H}_k \rightarrow L^2(P)$ is given by

$$J^* : \begin{cases} L^2(P) & \rightarrow & \mathcal{H}_k \\ g & \mapsto & E_P(g\phi_k) = \int_{\mathcal{X}} g(y)k_y P(dy). \end{cases}$$

Proof. Let us start by showing that J^* is well-defined. Since $g \in L^2(P)$ and $\phi_k \in L^2(P; \mathcal{H}_k)$, a simple application of Hölder's inequality shows $g\phi_k \in L^1(P; \mathcal{H}_k)$.

To see that J^* as stated is indeed the adjoint operator of J , let $f \in \mathcal{H}_k$ and $g \in L^2(P)$. We calculate

$$\begin{aligned} \langle g | Jf \rangle_{L^2(P)} &= \int_{\mathcal{X}} g(y)f(y)P(dy) = \int_{\mathcal{X}} g(y)\langle k_y | f \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_k} P(dy) \\ &= \left\langle \int_{\mathcal{X}} g(y)k_y P(dy) \middle| f \right\rangle_{\mathcal{H}_k} = \langle J^*g | f \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_k}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 3.22 ([SC08, Theorem 4.27, p. 127]):

Let k be a square-integrable kernel on the measurable space \mathcal{X} equipped with the probability measure P . The operators J and J^* are Hilbert-Schmidt operators with $\|J\|_{\text{HS}} = \|J^*\|_{\text{HS}} = \|k\|_{L^2(P)}$.

Proof. Let $(e_k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ be an orthonormal basis of \mathcal{H}_k (remember that H_k is separable by definition of a square-integrable kernel and therefore has a countable basis). We obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \|J\|_{\text{HS}}^2 &= \text{tr}(J^*J) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \|Je_k\|_{L^2(P)}^2 = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \int_{\mathcal{X}} |e(x)|^2 P(dx) = \int_{\mathcal{X}} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |e(x)|^2 P(dx) \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{X}} \underbrace{\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |\langle k_x | e_k \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_k}|^2}_{=\|k_x\|_{\mathcal{H}_k}^2} P(dx) = \|k\|_{L^2(P)}^2. \end{aligned}$$

It is a general fact from functional analysis that an operator is a Hilbert-Schmidt operator if and only if its adjoint is and that both Hilbert-Schmidt norms coincide (see [Wer18, Satz VI.6.2 (b), p. 321]). □

We now have everything to introduce the integral operator on L^2 associated with the kernel k .

Theorem 3.23 (The kernel integral operator, [SC08, Theorem 4.27, p. 127]):

Let k be a square-integrable kernel on the measurable space \mathcal{X} equipped with the probability measure P . Then the operator $T_k := JJ^* : L^2(P) \rightarrow L^2(P)$ is given by

$$T_k : \begin{cases} L^2(P) & \rightarrow & L^2(P) \\ g & \mapsto & \int_{\mathcal{X}} k(\cdot, y)g(y)P(dy). \end{cases}$$

It is a self-adjoint, positive semidefinite, trace-class operator whose trace norm is given by $\|T_k\|_{\mathcal{N}(L^2(P))} = \|k\|_{L^2(P)}^2 = \int_{\mathcal{X}} k(x, x)P(dx)$.

Proof. Let $g \in L^2(P)$. Let us evaluate J^*g at $x \in \mathcal{X}$:

$$J^*g(x) = \langle k_x | J^*g \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_k} = \left\langle k_x \left| \int_{\mathcal{X}} k_y g(y)P(dy) \right\rangle_{\mathcal{H}_k} = \int_{\mathcal{X}} \underbrace{\langle k_x | k_y \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_k}}_{=k(x,y)} g(y)P(dy).$$

Applying J to J^*g merely causes J^*g to be taken as its L^2 equivalence class, which shows the stated expression.

It is by definition of $T_k = JJ^*$ clear that it is self-adjoint and positive semidefinite. It is also a trace class operator since it is a composition of two Hilbert-Schmidt operators (see [Wer18, Satz VI.6.2 (e), p. 321]). The trace norm is given by:

$$\|T_k\|_{\mathcal{N}(L^2(P))} = \text{tr}(|T_k|) = \text{tr}(JJ^*) = \|J\|_{\text{HS}}^2 = \|k\|_{L^2(P)}^2.$$

□

A first insight into the deep connection to the covariance operator can be seen in the following. Consider the operator $J^*J : \mathcal{H}_k \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_k$. When applying a function $f \in \mathcal{H}_k$ to it, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} J^*Jf &= \int_{\mathcal{X}} k_y f(y) P(dy) = \int_{\mathcal{X}} k_y \langle k_y | f \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_k} P(dy) \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{X}} |k_y\rangle \langle k_y| P(dy) f = E_X (|k_X\rangle \langle k_X|) f = \Sigma^{\text{uncen}} f, \end{aligned}$$

where $\Sigma^{\text{uncen}} := E_X (|k_X\rangle \langle k_X|) = J^*J$ is the “uncentered covariance operator” of the \mathcal{H}_k -valued random variable k_X . Here, X denotes a \mathcal{X} -valued random variable with probability distribution P .

The connection between the uncentered covariance operator and the integral operator is based on Lemma A.2 and A.3, which establish a close link of the spectral decomposition of the two operators.

The next section introduces kernel PCA and, among other things, lays out the exact relationship between the covariance operator and the integral operator T_k .

3.3. Kernel Principal Component Analysis

Kernel Principal Component Analysis is an extension of the PCA algorithm to handle nonlinear data. While PCA is an effective technique for analyzing linear data, it often struggles with high-dimensional data that contain complex, nonlinear patterns. This is particularly evident in the toy dataset shown in Figure 5, where KPCA is better suited to capture the intrinsic structure of the data than PCA.

As we have already covered the theory of Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Spaces in the previous chapter, we are now equipped to kernelize the PCA algorithm discussed in Chapter 2.

3.3.1. The Population Picture

Similar to Section 2.1, we assume that the true data distribution P on the sample space \mathcal{X} is known to us. Expressed more rigorously, let \mathcal{X} be a measurable space and X an \mathcal{X} -valued random variable with distribution P .

Further, let k be a (with respect to P) square-integrable kernel on \mathcal{X} and $\phi_k : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_k$ the associated canonical feature map, which is known to be measurable (see Lemma B.3).

We consider in the following the resulting \mathcal{H}_k -valued random variable $\phi_k(X) = k_X$. Since the kernel k is square-integrable, it follows by Definition 3.17 of square-integrable kernels that $k_X \in L^2(P; \mathcal{H}_k)$. Consequently, Lemma 2.2 is applicable and we obtain the existence

Figure 5: Contour plot comparing the first coordinate of the encoding obtained by PCA and KPCA using the kernel $k(x, y) = \langle x | y \rangle_{\mathbb{R}^2}^2$. The plot shows the variation of the encoding across different input samples, visualized using contour lines.

of the corresponding kernel covariance operator

$$\Sigma_k := E(|k_X - E(k_X)\rangle\langle k_X - E(k_X)|),$$

which is a self-adjoint, positive semidefinite trace class operator on \mathcal{H}_k .

Our goal now is to establish the connection to the integral operator T_k . To accomplish this, we proceed similarly as in Section 2.3 for the calculation of the PCA and decompose Σ_k . Before specifying the decomposition, we first introduce the projection operator

$$P_{\langle 1 \rangle^\perp} = I_{L^2(P)} - |1\rangle\langle 1| : \begin{cases} L^2(P) & \rightarrow L^2(P) \\ g & \mapsto g - E(g(X)), \end{cases}$$

which centers the random variable $f(X)$ derived from the $L^2(P)$ function f or, said more abstractly, projects an L^2 function orthogonally onto the orthogonal space of all constant functions.

We can now introduce the operators

$$L = P_{\langle 1 \rangle^\perp} J : \begin{cases} \mathcal{H}_k & \rightarrow L^2(P) \\ f & \mapsto f - E(f(X)) \end{cases}$$

and

$$L^* = J^* P_{\langle 1 \rangle^\perp} : \begin{cases} L^2(P) & \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_k \\ g & \mapsto E((g(X) - E(g(X))) k_X). \end{cases}$$

Remark 3.24. We can rewrite the operator L^* a bit in order to obtain other useful representations. Let $g \in L^2(P)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
L^*g &= E\left(\left((P_{\langle 1 \rangle^\perp}g)(X)\right)k_X\right) - \underbrace{\left\langle P_{\langle 1 \rangle^\perp}g \middle| 1 \right\rangle_{L^2(P)}}_{=0} E(k_X) \\
&= E\left(\left(g(X) - E(g(X))\right)\left(k_X - E(k_X)\right)\right) = \text{“Cov}(g(X), k_X)\text{”} \quad (13) \\
&= E\left(g(X)\left(k_X - E(k_X)\right)\right). \quad (14)
\end{aligned}$$

The following lemma verifies that Σ_k can indeed be decomposed in the above-defined operators.

Lemma 3.25 (Decomposition of the kernel covariance operator):

*The kernel covariance operator decomposes into $\Sigma_k = L^*L$.*

Proof. For $f \in \mathcal{H}_k$ we can rewrite $Lf = \langle \phi_k(\cdot) - E(k_X) | f \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_k}$ (considered as an L^2 -function). Using the representation of the operator L^* in Equation 14, we can now easily calculate that

$$L^*Lf = E\left(\left(k_X - E(k_X)\right)\left(Lf\right)(X)\right) = E\left(\left(k_X - E(k_X)\right)\langle k_X - E(k_X) | f \rangle_{\mathcal{H}_k}\right) = \Sigma_k f,$$

which shows that L^*L indeed gives the claimed decomposition of the covariance operator Σ_k . \square

Now we can switch the positions of the operators L and L^* . That way, similar to the centered Gram matrix in 11 (see also Remark 2.21), we obtain the centered kernel integral operator.

Definition 3.26 (Centered kernel integral operator). The *centered kernel integral operator* T_k^{cen} is defined by $T_k^{\text{cen}} := LL^* = P_{\langle 1 \rangle^\perp}JJ^*P_{\langle 1 \rangle^\perp} = P_{\langle 1 \rangle^\perp}T_kP_{\langle 1 \rangle^\perp}$.

Lemma 3.27 (Properties of the centered kernel integral operator):

The centered kernel integral operator T_k^{cen} is a self-adjoint, positive semidefinite trace class operator on $L^2(P)$.

Proof. The properties are all inherited directly from the kernel integral operator T_k (see Theorem 3.23). \square

The theorem below states the exact relationship between the kernel covariance operator and the centered kernel integral operator. Basically, the theorem states that instead of studying the spectral properties of the kernel covariance operator, we can study those of the centered kernel integral operator.

Theorem 3.28:

The kernel covariance operator Σ_k and the centered kernel integral operator T_k^{cen} have the same non-zero point spectrum, that is $\sigma_p(\Sigma_k) \setminus \{0\} = \sigma_p(T_k^{\text{cen}}) \setminus \{0\}$. Furthermore, if

$$T_k^{\text{cen}} = \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \sigma_l^2 |e_l\rangle \langle e_l|$$

is the spectral decomposition according to A.1, then we can construct the spectral decomposition of Σ_k by defining $u_l := \frac{1}{\sigma_l} L^* e_l$ for $l \in \mathbb{N}$. It is then given by

$$\Sigma_k = \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \sigma_l^2 |u_l\rangle \langle u_l|.$$

Proof. The theorem follows directly by applying Lemma A.2 and A.3 from the appendix. \square

We now turn to the representation of the data points from the sample space \mathcal{X} in \mathbb{R}^d . A data point $x \in \mathcal{X}$ is assigned the coordinates of the embedded data point k_x in the RKHS \mathcal{H}_k (see encoding map in Equation 2 of Chapter 2). That is, we get

$$\text{enc} : \begin{cases} \mathcal{X} & \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d \\ x & \mapsto (\langle u_l, k_x - E(k_X) \rangle)_{l=1}^d = (u_l(x) - E(u_l(X)))_{l=1}^d. \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

The next theorem shows us how to obtain the encoding map directly from the eigenfunctions of the centered integral operator.

Theorem 3.29 (Representation of the encoding coordinates via the eigenfunctions of the centered kernel integral operator):

The encoding map is given by $\text{enc}(x) = (\sigma_l e_l(x))_{l=1}^d$ for P -almost all $x \in \mathcal{X}$.

Proof. We use the representation $u_l = \frac{1}{\sigma_l} L^* e_l$ from Theorem 3.28. That way, we see for $x \in \mathcal{X}$

$$(\text{enc}(x))_l = \frac{1}{\sigma_l} (L^* e_l(x) - E(L^* e_l(X))) \stackrel{=}{=} \frac{1}{\sigma_l} \underbrace{LL^* e_l}_{\sigma_l^2 e_l} (x).$$

Unfortunately, the last equality is not rigorous, since $L^* L e_l$ is an L^2 function and therefore cannot be evaluated pointwise. The above –somewhat sloppy– calculation, however, can be transformed into a rigorous statement by taking the l -th coordinate of enc to be an L^2 function. This shows that $\sigma_l e_l$ is in the same L^2 equivalence class as the l -th coordinate of enc . In other words, both functions agree P -almost surely. \square

Remark 3.30. Now it becomes clear why the centering of the kernel integral operator T_k is essential. First, centering ensures that the eigenfunctions e_l itself are centered. But more importantly, it is desirable to project out the constant parts in the dimensional reduction task. For instance, if 1 were one of the first eigenfunctions of the centered kernel integral operator T_k^{cen} , the image of the encoding map would lie in a $d - 1$ dimensional affine hyperplane, reducing the dimensionality even more than originally intended.

3.3.2. The Sample Picture

In applications, we do not know the true distribution of X . However, we have n \mathcal{X} -valued observations X_1, \dots, X_n which we assume to be independently and identically distributed.

We therefore replace the unknown distribution P by the empirically observed distribution

$$P_n = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{X_i}.$$

This gives us the empirical kernel covariance operator

$$\Sigma_{k,n} := \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |k_{X_i} - \bar{k}_n\rangle \langle k_{X_i} - \bar{k}_n|,$$

where $\bar{k}_n := \frac{1}{n} \sum_{l=1}^n k_{X_l}$.

Since the n observations X_1, \dots, X_n are usually pairwise distinct, there is a canonical isometric isomorphism between the Hilbert spaces $L^2(P_n)$ and $\mathbb{R}_{\text{emp}}^n$ given by

$$\cdot \begin{cases} L^2(P_n) & \rightarrow & \mathbb{R}_{\text{emp}}^n \\ f & \mapsto & (f(X_i))_{i=1}^n. \end{cases}$$

Using this isomorphism, the kernel integral operator can be simplified to the kernel matrix defined by

$$K_n = \frac{1}{n} \begin{pmatrix} k(X_1, X_1) & k(X_1, X_2) & \cdots & k(X_1, X_n) \\ k(X_2, X_1) & k(X_2, X_2) & \cdots & k(X_2, X_n) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ k(X_n, X_1) & k(X_n, X_2) & \cdots & k(X_n, X_n) \end{pmatrix},$$

which acts on $\mathbb{R}_{\text{emp}}^n$.

The next step is then to compute the spectral decomposition of the centered kernel matrix

$$K_n^{\text{cen}} = P_{\langle 1_n \rangle^\perp} K_n P_{\langle 1_n \rangle^\perp} = \sum_{l=1}^{n-1} \hat{\sigma}_l^2 |v_l\rangle \langle v_l|.$$

We can now apply Theorem 3.29 to encode the observed data points X_1, \dots, X_n into \mathbb{R}^d .

Theorem 3.31 (Embedding of observed data points):

The observed data points are encoded by the KPCA algorithm via $\widehat{\text{enc}}(X_i) = (\hat{\sigma}_l(v_l)_i)_{l=1}^d$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$.

Remark 3.32. Note that we get the same results when applying Section 2.3 about the calculation of PCA to the Hilbert space valued random variable k_X .

The results there also show that the calculation presented here gives the correct results even if the observed data points are not necessarily pairwise distinct.

4. Manifold Learning

Manifold learning is a technique in machine learning to reduce the dimensionality of high-dimensional data while maintaining its intrinsic geometric properties, making it easier to analyze, visualize and understand. It is based on the assumption that many real-world datasets lie on or near a low-dimensional submanifold of \mathbb{R}^p , which can be thought of as a curved surface embedded in a higher-dimensional space.

There are many different methods and approaches in Manifold Learning. Here, we will mainly study the so-called Diffusion Maps algorithm. The Diffusion Maps algorithm constructs a graph on the data, approximating the underlying manifold, and then creates a Markov process on the data points. By measuring the probabilities of transitioning between points, it reveals the intrinsic structure and provides a lower-dimensional representation that preserves the important relationships within the data.

Our main objectives are on the one hand to present the Diffusion Maps algorithm in a new way that reveals a close connection to Brownian motion on a Riemannian manifold and provides a better rationale for the construction of the algorithm. On the other hand, we establish a connection to Kernel Principal Component Analysis.

4.1. Basic Definitions of Differential Geometry

In this section, we introduce some fundamental concepts in differential geometry, namely manifolds, Riemannian manifolds, and the volume measure on a Riemannian manifold. While these concepts have precise mathematical definitions, our focus will be on developing an intuitive understanding of their geometric properties and how they relate to one another. We will therefore present the definitions in a way that emphasizes their geometric meaning, rather than their technical details.

A d -dimensional *manifold* \mathcal{M} is informally a (topological) space that looks locally like the d -dimensional Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^d , but may have a more complicated global structure. This is very similar to our daily experience on planet earth, which looks flat from our local perspective.

Looking locally like the Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^d means more precisely that each point $x \in \mathcal{M}$ admits an open neighborhood $U \subseteq \mathcal{M}$ and a homeomorphism $\varphi : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$. Such a pair (U, φ) is called a *chart* of the manifold. A family of charts $(U_i, \varphi_i)_{i \in I}$ that covers the entirety of the manifold \mathcal{M} is called an *atlas*.

Let us state a formal definition of manifolds

Definition 4.1 (d -dimensional (smooth) manifolds [Lee12, pp. 2-3 and p. 13]). A topological space \mathcal{M} is called a d -dimensional *topological manifold* if it is locally homeomorphic to \mathbb{R}^d and has the two additional properties of being Hausdorff and second countable.

We call a topological manifold a *smooth manifold* if it is equipped with a maximal smooth

atlas, also known as a *smooth structure*.

An atlas $(U_i, \varphi_i)_{i \in I}$ is thereby smooth if all of the transition maps $\varphi_i \circ \varphi_j : \varphi_j(U_i \cap U_j) \rightarrow \varphi_i(U_i \cap U_j)$ are smooth.

The second countability and the Hausdorff property are mainly required to exclude pathological cases. The smooth structure allows us to introduce calculus on the manifold.

A *Riemannian manifold* is an object that combines the notions of a smooth manifold and a Riemannian metric. A Riemannian metric is a smoothly varying inner product on each tangent space, which allows us to measure lengths and angles on a manifold.

More formally:

Definition 4.2 (Riemannian manifolds [Lee18, p. 11]). A *Riemannian manifold* is a pair (\mathcal{M}, g) , where \mathcal{M} is a smooth manifold and g is a function that assigns to each point $p \in \mathcal{M}$ a scalar product of the tangent space $T_p\mathcal{M}$:

$$g_p : T_p\mathcal{M} \times T_p\mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathbb{R},$$

that depends smoothly on p .

The geodesic distance between two points $x, y \in \mathcal{M}$, for example, can then be calculated as the infimum over all possible path lengths $L(\gamma) := \int_0^1 g_{\gamma(t)}(\dot{\gamma}(t), \dot{\gamma}(t)) dt$ of smooth paths $\gamma : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$ connecting x and y .

But the Riemannian metric does not only provide a notion of distance on the manifold, it also enables us to measure the volume of subsets of the manifold. This is accomplished by using the *Riemann-Lebesgue measure* $\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}$ on $(\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{M}))$ induced by the Riemannian metric [AE09, pp. 392-396]. Good introductions and background on the Riemann-Lebesgue measure can be found in [Gri09, Section 3.4], [AE09, Chapter XII] and [Lee12, Chapter 16]. For us, it is sufficient here only to know about the existence.

While the definitions of manifolds and Riemannian manifolds might seem abstract at first, it is important to note that in our case we are primarily interested in submanifolds of Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^p . The reason for this is that the data points we are working with are typically numerical and thus lie in Euclidean space. This means that in practice, many of the manifolds we encounter will have a natural embedding in Euclidean space. For example, the set of all images of a particular object taken from different angles might naturally form a submanifold of \mathbb{R}^p , where p is the number of pixels in each image. Similarly, the set of all possible configurations of a robotic arm might form a submanifold of \mathbb{R}^p , where p is the number of degrees of freedom of the arm. In both cases, one expects the underlying data to lie on a manifold due to certain constraints or regularities in the problem, and manifold learning algorithms can be used to extract useful information and insights from the data. By using the rigorous framework of differential geometry and Riemannian geometry, we can develop powerful algorithms for analyzing and visualizing such high-dimensional data.

It should be noted that for our analysis, we will focus on compact Riemannian manifolds. This is because the numerical features of the data points are usually bounded in most practical applications, and furthermore, since there are only a finite number of data points, we can assume that the submanifold of \mathbb{R}^p on which they lie is bounded in Euclidean space. A notable characteristic of compact Riemannian manifolds is that they possess finite volume.

Lemma 4.3 ([Gri09, Theorem 3.11, pp. 59-60]):

A compact Riemannian manifold has finite Riemann-Lebesgue measure, that is, $\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M}) < \infty$.

By normalizing, this allows us to define the uniform distribution $\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{M})$ on \mathcal{M} via $\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{M})(A) := \frac{\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(A)}{\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M})}$ for $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{M})$.

4.2. The Heat Kernel on a Manifold

The heat kernel plays a crucial role in manifold learning because it provides a natural way to measure the similarity between points on a manifold. Specifically, it describes how heat diffuses on the manifold over time by computing the probability that a diffusion process starting at one point will reach another point after a certain amount of time. This allows us to construct a diffusion process on the manifold, which serves as the foundation of the popular Diffusion Maps algorithm for nonlinear dimensionality reduction.

In this subsection, we will introduce the heat kernel on manifolds and explore some of its essential properties, which will be crucial in our subsequent study of the Diffusion Maps algorithm.

The heat kernel in the Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^d is a well-known concept and is given by

$$p_t^{\mathbb{R}^d}(x, y) = (2\tau t)^{-\frac{d}{2}} \exp\left(-\frac{\|x - y\|_{\mathbb{R}^d}^2}{4t}\right),$$

where $\tau := 2\pi$ is the alternative circle constant¹. It is the fundamental solution to the heat equation $\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^d} u$, which describes the evolution of a heat distribution in Euclidean space over time.

We are also able to study heat evolution on a Riemannian manifold via the equation

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \Delta_{\mathcal{M}} u, \tag{16}$$

where $\Delta_{\mathcal{M}}$ is the Laplace-Beltrami operator on the Riemannian manifold, which generalizes the Laplace operator on Euclidean space and is also defined as the divergence of the

¹Good reasons for the usage of τ (tau) instead of π (pi) are discussed in *The Tau Manifesto* by Michael Hartl. See <https://tauday.com/tau-manifesto>.

gradient. The exact calculation in terms of the Riemannian metric is, however, not required for our purposes. More background information can be found in [Gri09, Chapter 3].

It is now not surprising that the concept of a heat kernel also generalizes to the manifold setting.

The following theorem establishes the existence of a unique heat kernel on a Riemannian manifold and lists the for our purposes most important properties, which should already be familiar from the Euclidean heat kernel.

Theorem 4.4 ([Gri09, Theorem 7.13, Remark 7.14 and Theorem 7.20, pp. 198-201 and pp. 208-210]):

Let (\mathcal{M}, g) be a Riemannian manifold. Then there exists for any $t \in (0, \infty)$ a unique function $p_t^{\mathcal{M}} : \mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ fulfilling the following properties:

- *Smoothness:* The function $p^{\mathcal{M}} : (0, \infty) \times \mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, (t, x, y) \mapsto p_t^{\mathcal{M}}(x, y)$ is smooth.
- $p_t^{\mathcal{M}}$ is a kernel for all $t \in (0, \infty)$, meaning that it is symmetric and positive semidefinite.
- *Non-negativity:* $p_t^{\mathcal{M}}(x, y) \geq 0$ for all $x, y \in \mathcal{M}$ and $t \in (0, \infty)$.
- *Sub-Markov property:* for all $x \in \mathcal{M}$ and $t \in (0, \infty)$,

$$\int_{\mathcal{M}} p_t^{\mathcal{M}}(x, y) \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dy) \leq 1.$$

- *The semigroup identity:* for all $x, y \in \mathcal{M}$ and $s, t \in (0, \infty)$,

$$p_{t+s}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, y) = \int_{\mathcal{M}} p_t^{\mathcal{M}}(x, z) p_s^{\mathcal{M}}(z, y) \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dz).$$

- For any $y \in \mathcal{M}$ the function $u(t, x) := p_t^{\mathcal{M}}(x, y)$ satisfies the heat equation (16).
- For all $f \in L^2(\mathcal{M})$ we have

$$e^{t\Delta_{\mathcal{M}}} f = \int_{\mathcal{M}} p_t^{\mathcal{M}}(x, y) f(y) \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dy),$$

where the family of exponentials $(e^{t\Delta_{\mathcal{M}}})_{t \in (0, \infty)}$ is the heat diffusion semigroup, which is defined via spectral calculus (see [Gri09, Chapter 4] for details).

Supplement to the proof. The heat kernel from the cited source is defined in [Gri09, p. 198, Equation 7.48] as an inner product and is thus a kernel. The remainder of the proof can be found in the cited source. \square

The heat kernel of a Riemannian manifold \mathcal{M} can give rise to a Markov semigroup on \mathcal{M} if it satisfies the stronger Markov property instead of the sub-Markov property. A Riemannian manifold with this property is called *stochastically complete*.

Definition 4.5 (Stochastic completeness, [Gri09, p. 231, Definition 8.17]). A Riemannian Manifold \mathcal{M} is called *stochastically complete* if the heat kernel $p_t^{\mathcal{M}}$ satisfies the Markov property

$$\int_{\mathcal{M}} p_t^{\mathcal{M}}(x, y) \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dy) = 1,$$

for all $t \in (0, \infty)$ and $x \in \mathcal{M}$.

Remarkably, the Markov semigroup on a stochastically complete Riemannian manifold \mathcal{M} defined by $k_t^{\mathcal{M}}(x, dy) := p_{t/2}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, y) \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dy)$ for $t \in (0, \infty)$ extends the concept of Brownian motion to the manifold setting, giving rise to a Brownian motion $(B_t^{\mathcal{M}})_{t \in [0, \infty)}$ on \mathcal{M} . In the case of $\mathcal{M} = \mathbb{R}^d$, the resulting Markov process is the well-known d -dimensional (pre-)Brownian motion $(B_t^{\mathbb{R}^d})_{t \in [0, \infty)}$ (see [Kle20, Example 14.48, p. 325] for the construction in \mathbb{R}^d).

Remark 4.6 (Brownian motion on stochastically incomplete Riemannian manifolds). It is possible to define the concept of Brownian motion on stochastically incomplete Riemannian manifolds as well. However, in this case, the overall probability is not conserved, as the Brownian motion can escape to infinity in finite time. This phenomenon is known as the *explosion* of Brownian motion and is equivalent to stochastic incompleteness.

As discussed previously, our focus is mainly on compact Riemannian manifolds. The fact that these manifolds are compact implies that it is not possible for Brownian motion to escape to infinity. This observation is confirmed by the following proposition:

Proposition 4.7 (Stochastic completeness of compact Riemannian manifolds, [Gri09, p. 233]):

Every compact Riemannian manifold \mathcal{M} is stochastically complete.

4.3. The Diffusion Maps Algorithm

The Diffusion Maps algorithm, developed by Ronald R. Coifman and Stéphane Lafon in [Laf04], [Coi+05], and [CL06], is a nonlinear dimensionality reduction technique. It involves generating a set of embeddings of the data in Euclidean space by utilizing the spectral decomposition of a diffusion operator defined on the dataset.

In this section, we will present the Diffusion Maps algorithm within a slightly different context than that described in the original papers. Initially, we assume a complete understanding of the underlying manifold \mathcal{M} . We demonstrate how the concept of Brownian motion $(B_t^{\mathcal{M}})_{t \in [0, \infty)}$ and the associated intrinsic heat kernel $p_t^{\mathcal{M}}$ of the manifold can assist us in obtaining a low-dimensional representation of the points residing on the manifold.

Subsequently, we move beyond the realm of complete knowledge and introduce a random walk on the sample data points. To achieve this, we approximate the underlying manifold by constructing a graph based on the data points. By leveraging the local Euclidean properties of the manifold, we replace the intrinsic heat kernel of \mathcal{M} with the heat kernel in flat space, effectively capturing the diffusion process over the graph approximation.

4.3.1. The Population Picture

In this section, we assume that we possess perfect knowledge of the smooth submanifold \mathcal{M} of the ambient space \mathbb{R}^p from which the data points are uniformly sampled. Since \mathcal{M} is a submanifold of \mathbb{R}^p , it naturally becomes a Riemannian manifold with the Riemannian metric inherited from the Euclidean ambient space. We further assume from now on that the manifold \mathcal{M} is compact and connected.

As shown in section 4.2, the diffusion process of Brownian motion $(B_t^{\mathcal{M}})_{t \in [0, \infty)}$ can be defined on \mathcal{M} with the Markov semigroup given by the transition kernels:

$$k_t^{\mathcal{M}}(x, dy) := p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, y) \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dy).$$

Before delving into how this diffusion process enables us to find a lower-dimensional representation of the points on the manifold, we define the associated diffusion operator semigroup and investigate the stationary measure of the diffusion process.

Definition 4.8 (The diffusion operator semigroup on \mathcal{M}). The *diffusion operator* on \mathcal{M} associated with time $t \in (0, \infty)$ is defined as follows:

$$P_t = e^{\frac{t}{2} \Delta_{\mathcal{M}}} : \begin{cases} L^2(\mathcal{M}) & \rightarrow L^2(\mathcal{M}) \\ f & \mapsto \int_{\mathcal{M}} k_t^{\mathcal{M}}(\cdot, dy) f(y) = \int_{\mathcal{M}} p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(\cdot, y) f(y) \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dy) \end{cases}$$

and $P_0 := \text{id}_{L^2(\mathcal{M})}$. Together they constitute the *diffusion operator semigroup* $(P_t)_{t \in [0, \infty)}$.

Proposition 4.9 (Properties of diffusion operators):

The diffusion operators P_t are well-defined, self-adjoint, positive semidefinite, trace-class operators for $t \in (0, \infty)$.

Proof. By Theorem 4.4, we know that the heat kernel is a kernel. Therefore, we can directly apply Theorem 3.23 to the auxiliary kernel $k = \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M}) p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}$ and use the uniform distribution on \mathcal{M} as the probability measure. Note that the auxiliary kernel is square-integrable since the heat kernel is continuous on the compact manifold and thus bounded. \square

The next proposition shows that the uniform distribution is an invariant measure of the Brownian motion Markov process.

Proposition 4.10 (Invariant measure of Brownian motion):

The uniform distribution $\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{M})$ is an invariant measure of the Markov semigroup $(k_t^{\mathcal{M}})_{t \in [0, \infty)}$ associated with Brownian motion. In other words,

$$\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{M}) * k_t^{\mathcal{M}} = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{M})$$

for all $t \in (0, \infty)$.

Proof. Let $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{M})$. Then we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{M}) * k_t^{\mathcal{M}}(A) &= \frac{1}{\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M})} \int_{\mathcal{M}} \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dx) k_t^{\mathcal{M}}(x, A) \\
&= \frac{1}{\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M})} \int_{\mathcal{M}} \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dx) \int_A \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dy) p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, y) \\
&\stackrel{\text{Fubini}}{=} \frac{1}{\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M})} \int_A \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dy) \underbrace{\int_{\mathcal{M}} \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dx) p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, y)}_{=1 \text{ by stochastic completeness of } \mathcal{M}} \\
&= \frac{\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(A)}{\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M})} = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{M})(A).
\end{aligned}$$

In the final step, we leveraged the stochastic completeness of compact Riemannian manifolds, as presented in Proposition 4.7, along with the symmetry property of the heat kernel. \square

The Diffusion Maps algorithm aims to preserve the so-called diffusion distance, denoted as $D_t(x, y)$, between two points x and y on the manifold \mathcal{M} . This distance is defined as the L^2 -distance between the transition probability density functions $p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, \cdot)$ and $p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(y, \cdot)$, weighted by the inverse of the density of the stationary measure $\Pi(dx) = \pi(x) \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dx)$.

Definition 4.11 (The diffusion distance [CL06, p. 9]). The *diffusion distance* for a given time $t \in (0, \infty)$ is defined as follows:

$$D_t(x, y)^2 = \left\| p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, \cdot) - p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(y, \cdot) \right\|_{L^2(\mathcal{M}, \frac{1}{\pi} \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}})}^2 = \int_{\mathcal{M}} \left| p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, z) - p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(y, z) \right|^2 \frac{\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dz)}{\pi(z)}.$$

In our specific case, the stationary measure is given by $\Pi = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{M})$, which implies that $\pi(x) = \frac{1}{\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M})}$. The diffusion distance can be thus simplified as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
D_t(x, y)^2 &= \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M}) \left\| p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, \cdot) - p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(y, \cdot) \right\|_{L^2(\mathcal{M})}^2 \\
&= \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M}) \int_{\mathcal{M}} \left| p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, z) - p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(y, z) \right|^2 \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dz). \tag{17}
\end{aligned}$$

Excursion to the spectral theory of the Laplace-Beltrami operator on compact manifolds

In order to obtain a lower-dimensional representation of points on a manifold while preserving the diffusion distance, we introduce the spectral decomposition of the Laplace-Beltrami operator.

Theorem 4.12 (Sturm-Liouville decomposition of the Laplace-Beltrami operator [Cha84, pp. 139-141]):

Let \mathcal{M} be a compact and connected Riemannian manifold. Then there exists a complete

orthonormal basis $(\phi_k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}_0}$ of $L^2(\mathcal{M})$ consisting of smooth eigenfunctions of $-\Delta_{\mathcal{M}}$, that is,

$$-\Delta_{\mathcal{M}}\phi_k = \mu_k\phi_k$$

for all $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$, whereby the eigenvalues satisfy

$$0 = \mu_0 < \mu_1 \leq \mu_2 \leq \dots \rightarrow \infty,$$

which implies that each eigenvalue has finite multiplicity.

Furthermore, the eigenfunction ϕ_0 to the eigenvalue 0 is a constant.

With the help of this decomposition it is not surprising that the heat kernel $p_t^{\mathcal{M}}$ can be decomposed in terms of the spectral decomposition of $\Delta_{\mathcal{M}}$. The following theorem is essentially a consequence of Mercer's theorem [SC08, Theorem 4.49, p.150] and the above Theorem 4.12.

Proposition 4.13 (Mercer decomposition of the heat kernel [Cha84, pp. 139-141]):
For each time $t \in (0, \infty)$, the heat kernel $p_t^{\mathcal{M}}$ on the compact Riemannian manifold \mathcal{M} can be decomposed as follows:

$$p_t^{\mathcal{M}}(x, y) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} e^{-t\mu_k} \phi_k(x)\phi_k(y),$$

for all $x, y \in \mathcal{M}$. The convergence of the decomposition is absolute and uniform.

After this small excursion, we are ready to compute the diffusion distance and obtain an encoding of the points on the manifold. With the decomposition of Proposition 4.13 we can write $p_{t/2}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, \cdot) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{t}{2}\mu_k} \phi_k(x)\phi_k(\cdot)$. (Note that this sum converges in $L^2(\mathcal{M})$ since uniform convergence implies L^2 -convergence on measure spaces of finite measure.) Plugging this in into Equation 17, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} D_t(x, y) &= \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M}) \left\| p_{t/2}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, \cdot) - p_{t/2}^{\mathcal{M}}(y, \cdot) \right\|_{L^2(\mathcal{M})}^2 \\ &= \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M}) \left\| \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{t}{2}\mu_k} (\phi_k(x) - \phi_k(y)) \phi_k \right\|_{L^2(\mathcal{M})}^2 \\ &= \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M}) \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} e^{-t\mu_k} |\phi_k(x) - \phi_k(y)|^2. \end{aligned}$$

Note that the first term in the expansion of $p_{t/2}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, \cdot)$ cancels since ϕ_0 is constant.

It is now apparent that the following mapping represents an encoding of the points on

the manifold that preserves the diffusion distance associated to time $t \in (0, \infty)$:

$$: \begin{cases} \mathcal{M} & \rightarrow & \ell^2 \\ x & \mapsto & \sqrt{\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M})} (e^{-\frac{t}{2}\mu_k} \phi_k(x))_{k=1}^{\infty}. \end{cases}$$

Since the sequence of eigenvalues $(\mu_k)_{k=1}^{\infty}$ is increasing, we can for example define $d := \max \left\{ k \in \mathbb{N} \mid e^{-\frac{t}{2}\mu_k} \geq \delta e^{-\frac{t}{2}\mu_1} \right\}$ for a preset accuracy $\delta \in (0, 1)$. By truncating the above encoding we obtain a finite-dimensional representation of the points on the manifold.

Definition 4.14 (Diffusion maps [CL06, p. 10]). For each time $t \in (0, \infty)$ and fixed choice of dimension $d \in \mathbb{N}$ we obtain the encoding map

$$\Psi_t : \begin{cases} \mathcal{M} & \rightarrow & \mathbb{R}^d \\ x & \mapsto & \sqrt{\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M})} (e^{-\frac{t}{2}\mu_k} \phi_k(x))_{k=1}^d. \end{cases}$$

This is the *diffusion map* associated with time t .

Remark 4.15. In [CL06], the initial step involves constructing a discrete Markov process using a kernel function k defined on \mathcal{M} . An important characteristic of this kernel is its non-negativity, making it a suitable similarity measure between points. The transition probabilities of the Markov process are then assumed to be proportional to this similarity measure.

In our approach, we present the algorithm utilizing the intrinsic heat diffusion kernel of the manifold. This approach offers several benefits, including the direct incorporation of the manifold's geometry through the heat kernel. Furthermore, when dealing with a finite sample of data points on the manifold, it provides us with a clear motivation for constructing a graph based on the data points. By defining a Markov chain on these data points using the graph, we will gain insight into why the Gaussian kernel $k_{\gamma}(x, y) = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\gamma} \|x - y\|_{\mathbb{R}^p}^2\right)$ is commonly employed to weight the graph edges.

4.3.2. The Sample Picture

We now depart from our omniscient perspective and demonstrate how we construct a Markov chain on the data points that approximates the previously considered Markov process on the manifold.

To do this, we proceed in two steps. First, we show how we would construct the Markov chain on the data points if we knew the underlying manifold and its associated heat kernel.

Subsequently, we demonstrate how we can replace the intrinsic heat kernel of the manifold with the heat kernel in the flat Euclidean space, taking advantage of the local Euclidean nature of the manifold. A spectral decomposition of the transition matrix P of the Markov chain then provides the desired low-dimensional representation of the data points.

Construction of Markov Chain on Data Points

We assume having n data points X_1, \dots, X_n in \mathbb{R}^p sampled uniformly from a compact

and connected submanifold \mathcal{M} of \mathbb{R}^p .

If we knew the manifold, a natural assumption would be to choose the transition probability p_{ij} from data point X_i to data point X_j proportional to the transition probability density $p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(X_i, X_j)$ on the manifold:

$$p_{ij} \propto p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(X_i, X_j).$$

Hence, we obtain the transition probabilities by normalizing them with the factor $d_i := \sum_{k=1}^n p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(X_i, X_k)$:

$$p_{ij} = \frac{1}{d_i} p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(X_i, X_j).$$

An alternative perspective involves constructing a complete weighted graph on the data points. The vertex set is denoted as $V := \{X_1, \dots, X_n\}$, and each edge $e = X_i X_j$ is assigned a weight $w_{ij} = p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(X_i, X_j)$, resulting in the formation of the *weighted adjacency matrix* $W := (w_{ij})_{i,j=1}^n$.

The degree of a vertex X_i is defined as the sum of weights of the edges incident to it, given by:

$$\deg(X_i) := \sum_{l=1}^n w_{il}.$$

These degrees are consolidated into the diagonal matrix known as the *degree matrix* $D := \text{diag}(\deg(X_1), \dots, \deg(X_n))$.

Finally, the *transition probability matrix* P is given as $P := D^{-1}W$, resulting in a stochastic matrix.

Remark 4.16. The selected time parameter, denoted as $t \in (0, \infty)$, takes the role of a hyperparameter in this construction and requires adjustment. Typically, a small value is chosen for t , the specific choice of which depends on the number of available data points. When the combination of a too small t and sparse data is employed, the theoretical probability “bump function” $p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(X_i, \cdot)$ becomes concentrated around the data point X_i , resulting in a high weight w_{ii} and very small weights on the edges connecting X_i with other data points. Consequently, the Markov chain exhibits a tendency to remain at the current location with a high probability.

Next, we demonstrate a method to replace the intrinsic heat kernel of the unknown underlying manifold.

Considering the local Euclidean nature of \mathcal{M} , we anticipate that the heat kernel $p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}$ behaves similarly to the Euclidean heat kernel on a local scale. Assuming $d := \dim(\mathcal{M})$, we obtain the following approximation:

$$p_{t/2}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, y) \approx (\tau t)^{-\frac{d}{2}} \exp\left(-\frac{\text{dist}_{\mathcal{M}}(x, y)^2}{2t}\right),$$

where $x, y \in \mathcal{M}$ represent pairs of points that are “close” to each other on the manifold based on the geodesic distance $\text{dist}_{\mathcal{M}}(x, y)$.

In a subsequent step, utilizing the local Euclidian nature of \mathcal{M} once again, we can replace the geodesic distance with the ordinary Euclidean distance in the ambient space \mathbb{R}^p : $\text{dist}_{\mathcal{M}}(x, y) \approx \|x - y\|_{\mathbb{R}^p}$. This yields the following approximation for the heat kernel:

$$p_{t/2}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, y) \approx (\tau t)^{-\frac{d}{2}} \exp\left(-\frac{\|x - y\|_{\mathbb{R}^p}^2}{2t}\right),$$

applicable to two nearby points on the manifold. See also [Ros97, Chapter 3.3] for more details.

Conversely, when t is sufficiently small, the heat kernel $p_{t/2}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, y)$ becomes almost negligible for two “distant” points x and y on the manifold. This is because the transition probability density $p_{t/2}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, \cdot)$ is primarily concentrated around x , while y is comparatively far away.

Consequently, the aforementioned heuristic considerations motivate the construction of a graph that does not connect all data points on the manifold, but only links those with edges that are in close neighborhood to each other in some sense. There are two popular approaches to achieve this:

- **The ε -neighborhood approach:** In this approach, we introduce the hyperparameter $\varepsilon > 0$ and connect all data points X_i and X_j where the Euclidean distance $\|X_i - X_j\|_{\mathbb{R}^p}$ is less than or equal to ε .
- **The k -nearest neighbor approach:** In this approach, for each data point X_i , we determine its k nearest neighbors based on the Euclidean distance. We then connect two data points X_i and X_j if either X_j is among the k nearest neighbors of X_i or vice versa.

Based on this constructed graph, the weighted adjacency matrix $W = (w_{ij})_{i,j=1}^n$ is defined through:

$$w_{ij} = \begin{cases} \exp\left(-\frac{\|X_i - X_j\|_{\mathbb{R}^p}^2}{2t}\right), & \text{if } X_i \text{ and } X_j \text{ are adjacent,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

It is important to note that we can omit the prefactor $(\tau t)^{-\frac{d}{2}}$ of the Euclidean heat kernel, as it cancels out in the resulting transition probability matrix $P = D^{-1}W$. Fortunately,

this also eliminates the unknown intrinsic dimension d of the underlying manifold.

In summary, we have succeeded in eliminating any quantities that rely on the unknown manifold. The Markov chain constructed in this way serves as an approximation to the previously considered Markov process. The presentation we have chosen also explains, as previously mentioned in Remark 4.15, why the Gaussian kernel is a popular choice for constructing the Markov chain on the data points.

Spectral Decomposition of the Transition Probability Matrix P

We will now define the diffusion distance in the empirical case and perform the spectral decomposition of the above defined transition probability matrix P in order to get the desired lower-dimensional Diffusion Maps encodings.

Lemma 4.17 (Stationary distribution of P , [CL06, p. 9]):

A stationary distribution vector π of the transition probability matrix P is defined by

$$\pi_i = \frac{\deg(X_i)}{\sum_{k=1}^n \deg(X_k)},$$

for $i = 1, \dots, n$. It is unique, if the underlying graph is connected.

Proof. Note that $p_{ij} = \frac{1}{\deg(X_i)} w_{ij}$. We obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^n \pi_i p_{ij} &= \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\deg(X_i)}{\sum_{k=1}^n \deg(X_k)} \frac{1}{\deg(X_i)} w_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_{ij}}{\sum_{k=1}^n \deg(X_k)} \\ &= \frac{\deg(X_j)}{\sum_{k=1}^n \deg(X_k)} = \pi_j, \end{aligned}$$

which implies that $\pi^T P = \pi^T$. It is worth noting that we utilized the symmetry of the adjacency weight matrix W .

If the underlying graph is additionally connected, the Markov chain is irreducible, meaning that every state can be reached from any other state. The well-known theorem [LP17, Corollary 1.17, p. 13] from Markov chain theory ensures the existence of a unique stationary distribution for a irreducible Markov chain. \square

We will use this stationary distribution in the definition of the diffusion distance, even though the graph might not be connected.

Definition 4.18 (Empirical diffusion distance). We equip \mathbb{R}^n with a scalar product defined as follows:

$$\langle x | y \rangle_\pi := \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{\pi_k} x_k y_k,$$

for $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

The diffusion distance for the discrete time $m \in \mathbb{N}$ between two data point X_i and X_j is

then defined via

$$D_m(X_i, X_j)^2 := \left\| p_{i*}^{(m)} - p_{j*}^{(m)} \right\|_\pi^2 := \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{\pi_k} \left(p_{ik}^{(m)} - p_{jk}^{(m)} \right)^2,$$

where $p_{i*}^{(m)} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ represents the i -th row vector of the matrix P^m .

We proceed by decomposing $P = D^{-1}W$. For this purpose, we introduce the auxiliary matrix $A = D^{\frac{1}{2}}PD^{-\frac{1}{2}} = D^{-\frac{1}{2}}WD^{-\frac{1}{2}}$. Since A is symmetric, it can be decomposed using the spectral theorem for symmetric matrices as follows:

$$A = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \lambda_k \varphi_k \varphi_k^T,$$

where we assume $|\lambda_0| \geq |\lambda_1| \geq \dots \geq |\lambda_{n-1}|$ and $(\varphi)_{k=0}^{n-1}$ is an orthonormal basis in \mathbb{R}^n .

We now introduce the *volume* of the graph as $\text{vol}(G) := \sum_{l=1}^n \deg(X_l)$. Furthermore, we set $\phi_k := \sqrt{\text{vol}(G)} D^{-\frac{1}{2}} \varphi_k$ and $\psi_k := \frac{1}{\sqrt{\text{vol}(G)}} D^{\frac{1}{2}} \varphi_k$ for $k = 0, \dots, n-1$.

Proposition 4.19:

The following statements hold:

- *The vector systems $(\phi_k)_{k=0}^{n-1}$ and $(\psi_k)_{k=0}^{n-1}$ are biorthonormal, that is, $\langle \phi_i | \psi_j \rangle_{\mathbb{R}^n} = \delta_{ij}$. They constitute the right- and left-eigenvectors of P respectively.*
- *The vectors $(\psi_k)_{k=0}^{n-1}$ form an orthonormal basis of $(\mathbb{R}^n, \langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle_\pi)$.*
- *The matrix P^m can be decomposed as:*

$$P^m = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \lambda_k^m \phi_k \psi_k^T.$$

Proof. We have:

$$\langle \phi_i | \psi_j \rangle_{\mathbb{R}^n} = \left(\sqrt{\text{vol}(G)} D^{-\frac{1}{2}} \varphi_i \right)^T \frac{1}{\sqrt{\text{vol}(G)}} D^{\frac{1}{2}} \varphi_j = \varphi_i^T \varphi_j = \delta_{ij},$$

which shows the biorthonormality.

The scalar product $\langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle_\pi$ between two points $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ can be expressed as $\langle x | y \rangle_\pi = \text{vol}(G) x^T D^{-1} y$. Consequently,

$$\langle \psi_i | \psi_j \rangle_\pi = \text{vol}(G) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\text{vol}(G)}} D^{\frac{1}{2}} \varphi_i \right)^T D^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\text{vol}(G)}} D^{\frac{1}{2}} \varphi_j \right) = \varphi_i^T \varphi_j = \delta_{ij}.$$

Next, we write $P = D^{-\frac{1}{2}}AD^{\frac{1}{2}}$ and calculate:

$$\begin{aligned}
P^m &= D^{-\frac{1}{2}}A^mD^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
&= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \lambda_k^m \left(D^{-\frac{1}{2}}\varphi_k\right) \left(D^{\frac{1}{2}}\varphi_k\right)^T \\
&= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \lambda_k^m \left(\sqrt{\text{vol}(G)}D^{-\frac{1}{2}}\varphi_k\right) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\text{vol}(G)}}D^{\frac{1}{2}}\varphi_k\right)^T \\
&= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \lambda_k^m \phi_k \psi_k^T.
\end{aligned}$$

From this representation and the biorthonormality, it follows immediately, that $(\phi_k)_{k=0}^{n-1}$ are the right-eigenvectors of P while $(\psi_k)_{k=0}^{n-1}$ constitute the corresponding left-eigenvectors. \square

Lemma 4.20:

Let Q be a stochastic matrix. The spectral radius satisfies $\rho(Q) \leq 1$.

Proof. The spectral radius is bounded by any matrix norm. We choose the matrix norm based on the maximum norm, given by

$$\|Q\|_\infty = \max_{x \in S^{n-1}} \|Qx\|_\infty = \max_{i=1, \dots, n} \sum_{j=1}^n |q_{ij}|.$$

As all entries of Q are nonnegative and the rows sum up to 1, we obtain $\|Q\|_\infty = 1$. \square

We have seen that the stationary distribution π from Lemma 4.17 is a left-eigenvector with eigenvalue 1. Thanks to the previous lemma, we can assume without loss of generality that $\lambda_0 = 1$, with corresponding left- and right-eigenvectors $\psi_0 = \pi$ and $\phi_0 = 1_n$.

From the decomposition stated in Proposition 4.19, we obtain the representation $p_{i_*}^{(m)} = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \lambda_k^m (\phi_k)_i \psi_k$. Exploiting the fact that $(\psi_k)_{k=0}^{n-1}$ forms an orthonormal basis of $(\mathbb{R}^n, \langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle_\pi)$, we can now compute the diffusion distance:

$$\begin{aligned}
D_m(X_i, X_j)^2 &= \left\| p_{i_*}^{(m)} - p_{j_*}^{(m)} \right\|_\pi^2 = \left\| \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \lambda_k^m \left((\phi_k)_i - (\phi_k)_j \right) \psi_k \right\|_\pi^2 \\
&= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \lambda_k^{2m} \left| (\phi_k)_i - (\phi_k)_j \right|^2 = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \lambda_k^{2m} \left| (\phi_k)_i - (\phi_k)_j \right|^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Note that since $\phi_0 = 1_n$ is constant, we were able to leave out the first summand in the last step.

All the previous calculations finally lead to the following encoding of the data points:

Definition 4.21. For each discrete time $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and fixed choice of dimension $d \in \mathbb{N}$ we obtain the (empirical) encoding map

$$\hat{\Psi}_m : \begin{cases} \mathcal{S} := \{ X_1, \dots, X_n \} & \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d \\ X_i & \mapsto (\lambda_k^m (\phi_k)_i)_{k=1}^d. \end{cases}$$

This is the (*empirical*) *diffusion map* associated with the discrete time step m . In other words, the i -th data point is encoded as the i -th row of the matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} | & | & & | \\ \lambda_1^m \phi_1 & \lambda_2^m \phi_2 & \dots & \lambda_d^m \phi_d \\ | & | & & | \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}.$$

Figure 6: Data sampled uniformly from the half sphere on the left and the embedding generated by the diffusion map algorithm on the right. The sample was colored by the z -coordinate on the sphere.

Remark 4.22. The expectation is that this encoding closely resembles the theoretical encoding we derived in the population picture (see Definition 4.14). If the hyperparameter $t \in (0, \infty)$ is chosen for the graph construction, we anticipate that

$$\hat{\Psi}_m(X_i) \approx \Psi_{m \cdot t}(X_i),$$

for each $i = 1, \dots, n$, and the approximation improves as more data points are sampled from the manifold.

4.4. Connection to Kernel Principal Component Analysis

Thanks to our meticulous analysis of the algorithms presented so far, dividing them into population and sample perspectives, we can now easily establish a new, previously

unknown connection to the KPCA algorithm. It will turn out that in the population perspective, Diffusion Maps and Kernel PCA are two sides of the same coin under certain conditions.

In the Diffusion Maps algorithm, we implicitly mapped the points on the manifold through the feature map

$$\Phi : \begin{cases} \mathcal{M} & \rightarrow L^2\left(\mathcal{M}, \frac{1}{\pi} \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M})\right) \\ x & \mapsto p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, \cdot) \end{cases}$$

into the diffusion space $L^2\left(\mathcal{M}, \frac{1}{\pi} \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M})\right)$ and calculated the distances there. We can compute the associated kernel k_t for this feature map:

$$\begin{aligned} k_t(x, y) &= \langle \Phi(x) | \Phi(y) \rangle_{L^2(\mathcal{M}, \frac{1}{\pi} \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M}))} \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{M}} p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(x, z) p_{\frac{t}{2}}^{\mathcal{M}}(z, y) \frac{1}{1/\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M})} \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dz) \\ &= \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M}) p_t^{\mathcal{M}}(x, y). \end{aligned}$$

Here we used the semigroup identity from Theorem 4.4.

Now let us consider Kernel PCA with this kernel and the uniform distribution $\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{M})$ on \mathcal{M} as the population measure. The canonical feature map is

$$\phi_k : \begin{cases} \mathcal{M} & \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_{k_t} \\ x & \mapsto k_t(x, \cdot) = \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M}) p_t^{\mathcal{M}}(x, \cdot). \end{cases}$$

This yields as usual the corresponding kernel covariance operator Σ_{k_t} and the associated kernel integral operator is:

$$T_{k_t} : \begin{cases} L^2(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{M})) & \rightarrow L^2(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{M})) \\ f & \mapsto \int_{\mathcal{M}} p_t^{\mathcal{M}}(\cdot, y) f(y) \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(dy). \end{cases}$$

This coincides essentially with the heat diffusion operator (only the exact space on which it is defined is due to normalization slightly different). The spectral decomposition of T_{k_t} is thus

$$T_{k_t} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} e^{-\mu_k t} \left| \tilde{\phi}_k \right\rangle \left\langle \tilde{\phi}_k \right|,$$

where $\tilde{\phi}_k := \sqrt{\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M})} \phi_k$ are renormalized versions of the $L^2(\mathcal{M})$ -eigenfunctions $(\phi_k)_k$ of the heat diffusion operator from Theorem 4.12. Note that $\phi_0 = 1$ is constant. Thus

the centered kernel integral operator

$$\begin{aligned} T_{k_t}^{\text{cen}} &= P_{\langle 1 \rangle^\perp} T_{k_t} P_{\langle 1 \rangle^\perp} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} e^{-\mu_k t} \left| \tilde{\phi}_k \right\rangle \left\langle \tilde{\phi}_k \right| \end{aligned}$$

is simply obtained by dropping the term for $k = 0$.

The encoding map $\text{enc} : \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is consequently given by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{enc}(x) &= (e^{-\mu_1 \frac{t}{2}} \tilde{\phi}_1(x), \dots, e^{-\mu_d \frac{t}{2}} \tilde{\phi}_d(x))^T \\ &= \sqrt{\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M})} (e^{-\mu_1 \frac{t}{2}} \phi_1(x), \dots, e^{-\mu_d \frac{t}{2}} \phi_d(x))^T, \end{aligned}$$

for $x \in \mathcal{M}$. This is exactly the same encoding as in the Diffusion Maps algorithm (see Definition 4.14)!

In the population perspective, assuming that the data on the manifold is uniformly distributed, both approaches lead to the same outcome. In the Diffusion Maps algorithm, the central elements are the Markov process and the associated diffusion distance. On the other hand, the Kernel PCA algorithm involves mapping the manifold's data points to a feature space using a feature map and then projecting them into a lower-dimensional subspace through principal component analysis.

However, in the sample perspective, the two approaches diverge. In the Diffusion Maps algorithm, the focus is on replicating the Markov process on the data points, while in Kernel PCA, the unknown population measure is approximated using the empirical measure.

In the empirical case, directly performing Kernel PCA with the kernel $k_t = \text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M}) p_t^{\mathcal{M}}$ is not feasible due to the unknown manifold \mathcal{M} . However, the following points offer a way out:

- The prefactor $\text{vol}_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathcal{M})$ can be safely disregarded since it merely scales the resulting encoding.
- Instead of using the intrinsic heat kernel $p_t^{\mathcal{M}}$ in the kernel matrix, it can be substituted with the heat kernel of the ambient space \mathbb{R}^p , or alternatively, the Gaussian kernel. Another option is to approximate the intrinsic heat kernel by employing a graph construction, as discussed in the Diffusion Maps algorithm. This involves setting $K_n = \frac{1}{n} W$, where W represents the weighted adjacency matrix of the graph. However, it is worth noting that this approach has the drawback of the resulting kernel matrix generally not being positive semidefinite anymore.

References

- [AE08] Herbert Amann and Joachim Escher. *Analysis II*. 2nd ed. Birkhäuser, 2008. ISBN: 3764374721.
- [AE09] Herbert Amann and Joachim Escher. *Analysis III*. Birkhäuser, 2009. ISBN: 3764374799.
- [Aro50] Nachman Aronszajn. „Theory of reproducing kernels“. In: *Transactions of the American mathematical society* 68.3 (1950), pp. 337–404.
- [Cha84] Isaac Chavel. *Eigenvalues in Riemannian geometry*. Academic press, 1984.
- [CL06] Ronald R. Coifman and Stéphane Lafon. „Diffusion maps“. In: *Applied and computational harmonic analysis* 21.1 (2006), pp. 5–30.
- [Coi+05] Ronald R. Coifman et al. „Geometric diffusions as a tool for harmonic analysis and structure definition of data: Diffusion maps“. In: *Proceedings of the national academy of sciences* 102.21 (2005), pp. 7426–7431.
- [Gri09] Alexander Grigoryan. *Heat kernel and analysis on manifolds*. Vol. 47. American Mathematical Soc., 2009.
- [Kle20] Achim Klenke. *Probability Theory*. 3rd ed. Universitext. Springer, 2020. ISBN: 3030564010.
- [Laf04] Stéphane S Lafon. „Diffusion maps and geometric harmonics“. PhD thesis. 2004.
- [Lee12] John M. Lee. *Introduction to Smooth Manifolds*. 2nd ed. Springer New York, 2012. 724 pp. ISBN: 1441999817. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4419-9982-5.
- [Lee18] John M. Lee. *Introduction to Riemannian Manifolds*. Vol. 2. Springer, 2018. ISBN: 3319917544.
- [LP17] David A Levin and Yuval Peres. *Markov chains and mixing times*. Vol. 107. American Mathematical Soc., 2017.
- [LV07] John A. Lee and Michel Verleysen. *Nonlinear dimensionality reduction*. 1st ed. Springer, 2007. ISBN: 978-0-387-39350-6. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-39351-3>.
- [Mur22] Kevin P. Murphy. *Probabilistic machine learning: an introduction*. Adaptive computation and machine learning series. MIT press, 2022. ISBN: 978-0-262-04682-4. URL: <https://mitpress.mit.edu/9780262046824/>.
- [Pea01] Karl Pearson. „LIII. On lines and planes of closest fit to systems of points in space“. In: *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin philosophical magazine and journal of science* 2.11 (1901), pp. 559–572.
- [PR16] Vern I. Paulsen and Mrinal Raghupathi. *An introduction to the theory of reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces*. Vol. 152. Cambridge studies in advanced mathematics. Cambridge university press, Apr. 2016. ISBN: 978-1-107-10409-9.

- [Ros97] Steven Rosenberg. *The Laplacian on a Riemannian manifold : an introduction to analysis on manifolds*. eng. BV000841726 London Mathematical Society London Mathematical Society student texts 31. Cambridge, 1997. ISBN: 0521463009.
- [RW20] Markus Reiß and Martin Wahl. „Nonasymptotic upper bounds for the reconstruction error of PCA“. In: *The Annals of Statistics* 48.2 (2020), pp. 1098–1123. DOI: 10.1214/19-AOS1839. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1214/19-AOS1839>.
- [SC04] John Shawe-Taylor and Nello Cristianini. *Kernel methods for pattern analysis*. Cambridge university press, July 2004. ISBN: 978-0-521-81397-6.
- [SC08] Ingo Steinwart and Andreas Christmann. *Support vector machines*. Information science and statistics. Springer New York, 2008. ISBN: 978-0-387-77241-7. DOI: 10.1007/978-0-387-77242-4. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-77242-4>.
- [SS02] Bernhard Schölkopf and Alexander J. Smola. *Learning with kernels: support vector machines, regularization, optimization, and beyond*. Adaptive computation and machine learning. MIT press, 2002. ISBN: 978-0-262-19475-4.
- [Wer18] Dirk Werner. *Funktionalanalysis*. 8th ed. Springer, 2018. ISBN: 978-3-662-55406-7. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-55407-4>.

A. Functional Analysis

Theorem A.1 (Spectral Theorem for self-adjoint, compact operators [Wer18, Theorem VI.3.2 & Korollar VI.3.3, p. 294-296]):

Let H be a real Hilbert space. Furthermore, let $T \in K(H)$ be a compact, self-adjoint operator on that Hilbert space. Then there exists a countable (possibly finite) orthonormal basis (e_k) of $\ker(T)^\perp$ consisting of eigenvectors of T , such that

$$T = \sum_k \lambda_k |e_k\rangle \langle e_k|,$$

where (λ_k) is the corresponding sequence of eigenvalues, i.e. $Te_k = \lambda_k e_k$. The convergence (in case of $\ker(T)^\perp$ being infinite-dimensional) of the above sum is in the operator norm:

$$\left\| T - \sum_k^N \lambda_k |e_k\rangle \langle e_k| \right\|_{L(H)} \xrightarrow{N \rightarrow \infty} 0.$$

Moreover, the eigenvalues are real and the sequence of eigenvalues converges to 0 (in case the sequence is infinite).

Lemma A.2 (Point spectrum of swapped operators):

Let X and Y be two normed vector spaces. Furthermore, let $A \in L(X, Y)$ and $B \in L(Y, X)$. Then the operators $BA \in L(X)$ and $AB \in L(Y)$ have the same nonzero eigenvalues, i.e.

$$\sigma_p(BA) \setminus \{0\} = \sigma_p(AB) \setminus \{0\}.$$

More explicitly, if $x \in X$ is an eigenvector of BA to an eigenvalue $\lambda \neq 0$ then Ax is an eigenvector to the same eigenvalue of the operator AB .

Proof. Let $\lambda \in \sigma_p(BA) \setminus \{0\}$ be a nonzero eigenvalue and let $x \in X \setminus \{0\}$ be a corresponding eigenvector of BA . Multiplying the equation $BAx = \lambda x$ with A gives

$$AB(Ax) = \lambda(Ax).$$

Now note that $Ax \neq 0$, since we had otherwise $BAx = 0$ and this would contradict the nonzeroness of the eigenvalue λ .

We see now that $Ax \in Y \setminus \{0\}$ is an eigenvector of AB to the eigenvalue λ , which shows the inclusion $\sigma_p(BA) \setminus \{0\} \subseteq \sigma_p(AB) \setminus \{0\}$. Interchanging the roles of A and B in the above argument shows equality and finishes the proof. \square

Lemma A.3:

Let H_1 and H_2 be two Hilbert spaces and let $T \in L(H_1, H_2)$ be a bounded linear operator between them. Let further v_1 and v_2 be two normed and orthogonal eigenvectors of T^*T to the nonzero eigenvalues λ_1 and λ_2 .

Then

$$u_1 := \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda_1}} T v_1 \quad \text{and} \quad u_2 := \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda_2}} T v_2$$

are normed and orthogonal eigenvectors of the operator TT^* to the corresponding eigenvalues.

Proof. According to Lemma A.2 the vectors u_1 and u_2 are eigenvectors of TT^* to the corresponding eigenvalues. Let $i, j \in \{1, 2\}$. Then:

$$\langle u_i | u_j \rangle_{H_2} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda_i \lambda_j}} \langle T v_i | T v_j \rangle_{H_2} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda_i \lambda_j}} \langle v_i | T^* T | v_j \rangle_{H_1} = \frac{\lambda_j}{\sqrt{\lambda_i \lambda_j}} \underbrace{\langle v_i | v_j \rangle_{H_1}}_{=\delta_{ij}} = \delta_{ij}.$$

□

B. Properties of Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Spaces

Definition B.1 (Measurable kernels). Let \mathcal{X} be a measurable space and k be a kernel on \mathcal{X} . Then k is called *measurable* if $k(\cdot, x) : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is measurable for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$.

Lemma B.2 (RKHSs of measurable kernels, [SC08, Lemma 4.24, p. 125]):

Let \mathcal{X} be a measurable space and k be a measurable kernel on \mathcal{X} with RKHS \mathcal{H}_k . Then all $f \in \mathcal{H}_k$ are measurable.

Proof. A function $f \in \mathcal{H}_k$ can be written as a pointwise limit of the measurable functions in $\langle k_x | x \in \mathcal{X} \rangle$. □

Lemma B.3 (Measurability of the canonical feature map, [SC08, Lemma 4.25, p. 125]):

Let \mathcal{X} be a measurable space and k be a measurable kernel on \mathcal{X} . If the corresponding RKHS \mathcal{H}_k is separable, then both the canonical feature map $\phi_k : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_k$ and $k : \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are measurable.

Definition B.4 (Continuous kernels). Let \mathcal{X} be a topological space. A kernel k on \mathcal{X} is called *continuous* if it is continuous as a map from $\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X}$ to \mathbb{R} .

Lemma B.5 (Separable RKHSs, [SC08, Lemma 4.33, p. 130]):

Let \mathcal{X} be a separable topological space and k be a continuous kernel on \mathcal{X} . Then the corresponding RKHS \mathcal{H}_k is separable.

Selbstständigkeitserklärung

Ich erkläre, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit selbstständig verfasst und noch nicht für andere Prüfungen eingereicht habe. Sämtliche Quellen, einschließlich Internetquellen, die unverändert oder abgewandelt wiedergegeben werden, insbesondere Quellen für Texte, Grafiken, Tabellen und Bilder, sind als solche kenntlich gemacht. Mir ist bekannt, dass bei Verstößen gegen diese Grundsätze ein Verfahren wegen Täuschungsversuchs bzw. Täuschung eingeleitet wird.

Berlin, den 11. September 2023

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